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Food Sharing Governance Landscape Analysis in CULTIVATE hub locations: Barcelona

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1. Brief methodological note

The analysis of the governance landscape of food sharing initiatives in Barcelona required a mixture of methods and data sources. In order to maximise comparability between the three Hub cities, we developed a detailed research protocol to conduct the analysis of the food governance landscape. First, three research questions were defined to explore these governance landscapes:

- RQ1: How are regulatory regimes shaping food sharing landscapes, and what is their impact on FSIs?
- RQ2: What are the main place-based enablers for and barriers to sustainable food sharing in the three cities?
- RQ3: What is the influence of the cultural and socio-ecological context in shaping FSIs?
- The methodology employed a combination of desk-based research analysis and semistructured interviews with key informants in order to gather relevant data to address the research questions.

1.1 Desk-based research analysis

The online search mostly took place on local repositories, such as those from the local, regional, and national administrations. Members of the city administration partner of each local team provided valuable knowledge to identify relevant repositories. Additionally, this was complemented by Google searches adding key local words. We used a set of keywords for the online search. These were translated into Italian. Local teams also added extra keywords that they thought could be relevant considering the local context.

List of keywords:

- food sharing
- urban garden
- urban agriculture
- community garden
- community composting
- community kitchen
- community cooking
- food waste
- food redistribution
- food surplus
- social and solidarity economy AND food.

Documents were selected when they responded to relevant governance categories such as:

- Local strategic plans and programmes
- Legislation: bills, ordinances, regulations, etc.
- Projects
- Official reports

- Existing studies on food sharing governance of the specific city.

Each Hub location complemented this list with other types of documents that they considered relevant for conducting the analysis in their specific context.

1.2 Semistructured interviews

Each Hub location had to select between three and five participants for each of the food sharing arenas according to the following criteria:

- The sample had to cover the three food sharing arenas, taking into account the priority research topics of each Hub location.
- Interviewees had to have extensive experience in at least one of the food sharing arenas.
- The sample had to include participants who had taken part in the governance of FSIs at a diversity of administrative levels and positionalities.
- The sample had to include food sharing practitioners, government officials in relevant departments or agencies, and others if relevant.
- Most of the participants had to be based in the study location and familiar with its local context.
- The sample had to be gender diverse, and the inclusion of minority populations, when possible, had to be a priority. Each city will recruit a group of at least 10 key informants to be interviewed.

In Barcelona, we conducted 15 semi-structured interviews, which lasted 40 to 80 minutes. The interviews were recorded and anonymised. We transcribed and analysed them using the qualitative software Atlas.ti.

1.3 Analysis

The codification process for both the grey literature and the semi-structured interviews was based on a tree code category developed from a systematic literature review of academic articles focused on governance and food sharing. An initial tree code was developed and later discussed through a participative process with CULTIVATE partners, a total of 48 participants representing academia, policymakers and food sharing initiatives across Europe. The tree code aimed to identify potential barriers and enablers using two levels of categories. The first level listed eight broad categories of barriers and enablers: actors' discourses, internal organisation, knowledge, participation, regulations, relations between actors, resources, and structural factors. Each category contained a second level of codes representing the most relevant aspects of the first-level categories. We complemented the tree code during the process of analysis of the documents and interviews.

2. Community-Based Urban agriculture (CBUA)

2.1 Introduction

Barcelona has a population of 1.636.193 inhabitants and is one of the densest cities in Europe, with 16.144 h/m². (Idescat, 2023). In 2020, it had very low levels of urban green spaces per capita (7m² per inhabitant) (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2021), which represents approximately 38% of the green space per capita compared to an average calculated in a study from 386 European cities - which was 18,6m² per inhabitant (Fuller & Gaston, 2009). A decade ago, the Barcelona City Council (2013) estimated that not more than 0.3% of the city's surface was used for urban gardening. The limited spaces available for cultivation and the competition for space between urban gardening and other uses of public space (especially for housing development) is, as we will develop later, one of the main barriers to expanding urban gardening in the city.

Urban gardens in Barcelona have traditionally experienced a lack of interest from policymakers and the general public (Domene & Saurí, 2007). Historically, they have played an important role in food provisioning, and, for instance, during the civil war in 1938, there were 10.000 urban gardening plots in the city (Camps-Calvet et al., 2022). However, especially over the second half of the 20th century, agricultural production sites and horticulture gardens have been increasingly marginalised and expelled from the city through urbanisation processes (Roca, 2000).

Urban agriculture refers to all the different practice modalities of growing plants, fruits, and vegetables in urban areas. An in-depth analysis document written for The European Parliament differentiates between urban gardens and urban farms, mostly based on the different economic dependency of food production (James McEldowney, 2017). Since this report focuses on the intersection between food sharing and urban agriculture and not all urban agriculture entails a food-sharing component, it is important to discern between urban agricultural modes that constitute food-sharing initiatives and those that are not, as well as to understand further how food sharing urban agriculture takes place in the city of Barcelona. The main difference between these two categories relies on the different primary purposes of the urban agricultural projects and the different weight that productivity and economic benefit have over social and environmental benefits (i.e., productivity may also be relatively important in some cases, but not its primary purpose). Therefore, urban gardens involving food sharing, henceforth *food sharing gardens*, are urban gardens whose primary purpose is more related to the social benefits they offer (e.g., community-building, doing exercise, learning activity, etc.) than to their productive dimension, which might also play an important role, but it would not be the sole and primary aim.

In Barcelona, while food sharing gardens are limited in number, they are increasingly expanding throughout the city. They generally refer to one of the four categories: 1) community gardens, which are gardens for people from a community to use and enjoy. As we will explain later, there is a wide diversity of community gardens, including therapeutic and collectively squatted gardens; 2) allotment gardens, which are plots of land made available for individuals, families, or friends for cultivating purposes. While production is typically individualised in this category, we consider it part of food sharing because gardeners share knowledge, skills, tools, and time with neighbouring

gardeners in Barcelona; 3) social enterprise urban farms are projects run by organisations whose primary aim is serving the collective and/or general interest rather than making a profit; or 4) school gardens, which are gardens situated in schools that play a role in the educational curriculum. These four gardens' categories that give centrality to food sharing (see Table 1) differ from other urban agricultural projects excluded from this report, such as individual squatted gardens that precariously exist in the city's periphery and for-profit farming projects located in the municipality.

Table 1: Categories of food sharing gardens in Barcelona

Category of food sharing gardens	Description
Community gardens	These are gardens for people from a community to use and enjoy. There is a wide diversity of community gardens.
Allotment gardens	These are plots of land made available for individuals, families, or friends for cultivating purposes. While here production is typically individualised, we consider it part of food sharing because in Barcelona allotment gardeners share knowledge, skills, tools, and time with neighbouring gardeners.
Social enterprise urban farms	These are farming projects run by organisations whose primary aim is serving the collective and/or general interest rather than making a profit.
School gardens	These are gardens situated in schools that play a role in the educational curriculum.

Source: Own elaboration

According to the City Council website, there are 544 food sharing gardens (355 school gardens and 189 allotments and community gardens) (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2023a). Every so often, more food sharing gardens are discovered or pop up. Their communitarian dimension can vary in intensity: from only sharing tools, space, and time for cultivation to more joint organising processes in which the sharing dimension becomes more critical (e.g., joint decisions about the space, resources, activities, relations, etc.). As the report describes in more detail, there are many types of food sharing gardens depending on where they are located, how they are managed, in what sort of property regime they take place, and the openness of the gardens towards the gardeners and the neighbourhood. There is also a wide variety of users, including vulnerable social groups such as older people, people with physical or mental disabilities, and people with mental illness or injuries.

The primary goal of this report is to enhance comprehension of the governance landscape surrounding food sharing garden initiatives in Barcelona. This implies, on the one hand, understanding the regulatory framework that affects and conditions the practice of these activities, as well as knowing the map of actors involved, and understanding the type of relations formed between the actors involved in these initiatives. Also, understanding the food sharing gardens governance landscape involves appreciating and describing the diversity of shared food garden projects that exist in the city, as well as identifying who are their main beneficiaries. Furthermore, it is also crucial to recognize the main obstacles hindering the benefits of these initiatives and the

enablers that promote their success. The ultimate purpose of this report is to provide recommendations for the local government, shared food initiatives, and the private sector to support food sharing gardens expansion and improvement.

2.1.1 Brief methodological note

The analysis of the governance landscape of food sharing gardens in Barcelona involves a mixture of methods and data sources. First, we selected grey literature documents on urban gardens by navigating the city council website. We identified four main documents that were then analysed. Two of these documents were city strategies (i.e., the urban agricultural strategy and the healthy and sustainable food strategy), and two additional official documents analysed the main legal challenges of urban agriculture within the city.

We also contacted a key informant from the Barcelona municipality to understand the different City Council departments involved in food sharing gardens and identify significant stakeholders and projects. After we gathered this information, we shortlisted potential interviewees. We contacted six projects that had different characteristics (e.g., different management and different types of stakeholders). In the end, we conducted four semi-structured interviews. These interviews lasted from 40 to 80 minutes. The interviews were recorded and anonymised. We transcribed and analysed the interviews using the qualitative software Atlas.ti.

The codification process was based on a tree code category developed from a systematic literature review of academic articles focused on governance and food sharing. An initial tree code was developed and later discussed through a participative process with CULTIVATE partners, a total of 48 participants representing academia, policymakers and food sharing initiatives across Europe. The tree code aimed to identify potential barriers and enablers using two levels of categories. The first level listed eight broad categories of barriers and enablers: actors' discourses, internal organisation, knowledge, participation, regulations, relations between actors, resources, and structural factors. Each category contained a second level of codes representing the most relevant aspects of the first-level categories. We complemented the tree code during the process of analysis of the documents and interviews.

We have also conducted additional online searches, which have complemented our secondary data analysis including more than 35 food sharing garden websites, ten news articles about Barcelona's urban gardens in the press, and information from fifteen peer-reviewed papers on this topic with Barcelona as a case study.

2.2 Regulatory regimes shaping urban agriculture and food sharing gardens

2.2.1. Key policies, regulations, and plans regarding urban agriculture

2.2.1.1 Key regulations

Local, regional, and national regulations and policies affect urban gardening in Barcelona. However, key regulations and plans are primarily local, developed by the city council and the metropolitan area of Barcelona, and focus on urban planning and land use, as explained below.

At the local level, all urban gardens in Barcelona are affected by two urbanistic regulations. On the one hand, the **Metropolitan General Plan** is an urbanistic regulation affecting the urban area of Barcelona. In contrast, the other regulation, **PEPNat**, applies explicitly to the Barcelona part of the Natural Parc of Collserola. There is a significant difference between these two urbanistic regulations regarding urban agriculture: the former bans profitable agrarian activities within the urban area because there is no soil officially classified as non-developable there and, hence, food cannot be produced for commercialisation (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2020). Therefore, the only agricultural production that can legally occur in urban areas must be for self-supply. The production cannot be sold or donated. The latter plan, however, does allow selling the harvest, and in fact, we find some productive urban agriculture projects in this area. This significant difference potentially difficulties the city's expansion of food sharing gardening.

In Barcelona, urban agriculture has yet to be a primary focus of the local political agenda. While the first community garden ([Hort de l'Avi](#) - Gracia) was created in 1986 due to a petition from a neighbourhood association that squatted an empty plot to cultivate (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2023b), the first urban agriculture official program was only developed in 1997, namely the Urban Gardens Network (see the section on Municipal programs on urban gardens).

Only in recent years has the Barcelona City Council developed additional action plans and strategies to expand urban agriculture and open up the model specifically designed for older people towards a more diverse community-based model. The main plans affecting urban agriculture in the city are the following:

- **Green and Biodiversity Plan 2020 (2013):** This plan aims to expand organic farming in urban and periurban spaces, recognise the contribution of urban gardens to the city's biodiversity, and design a community-driven garden program.
- **Municipal Action Plan 2016-2019:** Continues with the same expanding aim for urban gardening while supporting community gardens and maximising social and environmental services.
- **Strategy of Urban Agriculture, 2019-2030 (SUA):** This is the primary local government tool for the city's urban gardens. It consolidates the previous plans and aims to promote agroecology and food sovereignty through urban gardens. It contains a SWOT analysis of urban gardens in Barcelona based on an extensive list of interviews with key stakeholders and five strategy goals and measures to expand urban agriculture in the city. These goals, which do not include quantitative targets nor reference to any budget, are:
 1. Increase cultivated surface to improve the urban quality space.
 2. Promote an agricultural model that enhances biodiversity.
 3. Promote agroecology to impact the agrifood system and consumption.
 4. Maximise social, therapeutical, and emotional benefits while promoting citizen participation and increasing active population, community management, and networks.
 5. Promote a shared governance model and implement municipal mechanisms to support urban agriculture.
- **2030 Healthy and Sustainable Food Strategy:** The first healthy and sustainable food strategy outlines nine main goals for urban food policies. The second goal, "expanding urban and

peri-urban agriculture,” includes the development of several measures and projects already mentioned at the SUA.

Additionally, in theory, a Spanish law affecting urban gardens is related to plant health. This is the **“Law 43/2002, from the 20th November, on plant health” (BOE, 2002)**. It refers to applying pesticides and fungicides to protect plants and the potential consequences of this activity for human and non-human animal health and the environment. Since urban food sharing gardens promote organic farming, prevention of damages caused by plagues and illnesses is, in theory, based mainly on enhancing protection from natural enemies, variety selection, crop rotations, and other organic farming techniques (EAU, 2019). However, there are no control mechanisms from the local government besides occasional surveys to ensure that gardeners practice organic farming.

Since some of the community gardens donate their surplus to food redistribution networks, in theory, this would imply a Catalan law also affecting this redistribution activity. This law is the **Catalan law 14/2003, from the 13th of June, on agrifood quality** (BOE, 2003): establishes the obligations of food operators to ensure the provision of quality food. This law could affect urban gardeners who donate surplus food to other organisations.

2.2.1.2 City Departments Involved in food sharing gardens

In Barcelona, different departments are involved in food sharing gardens (see Table 2) and are sometimes not fully coordinated. Only one technician is dedicated explicitly to urban gardens in the Ecology Department of the City Council, and the other departments do not have stable referent people on the topic.

Table 2: Departments from the Barcelona City Council involved in Food Sharing Gardens

Department	Function regarding urban agriculture
Municipal Insitute of Parks and Gardens located in the Department of Ecology, Urbanism, Infrastructures, Mobility, Public Space and Housing.	They manage the community garden programs and offer all the technical support for the Urban Agricultural Network program. They also produced the Urban Agriculture Strategy.
Municipal Institute of Disability	They manage the Gardens in Terraces program (see section on municipal programs) for users with disabilities.
Food Policy	They connect urban gardens with other food policy projects and make them visible.
Land Planning	They are responsible for zoning.
Districts	They receive and manage community petitions to create new gardens and sign agreements with gardening groups to allow them to use a plot. Two districts indirectly fund two community gardens by funding environmental education facilities.

Source: Own elaboration

2.2.1.3 Municipal programs on food sharing gardens

The main programs funded by the City Council that impact food sharing gardens in Barcelona are:

The [Urban Gardens network](#): The network of urban gardens in Barcelona is the first and possibly the main program developed by the City Council on urban gardening. Developed in 1997 by the Department of Environment, the program is designed for citizens over 65 years old who are given a free plot for cultivation for a maximum of 5 years. While a main requirement of these gardens is that cultivating techniques must be from organic farming and there are educational workshops for gardeners on the topic, there is no control mechanism to verify organic practices. This program currently involves the management of 15 urban gardens with 396 plots 25-40 m² in size. Management is present in all garden stages, from site preparation to covering expenses (water costs, materials, etc.) or even opening the premises for gardeners to enter their gardens for cultivation. There are currently 189 gardeners in this program (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2023a), although information regarding this program does not include total public expenses. Online information about the details and history of this program is challenging to find and appears scattered among different City Council websites. For instance, a piece of information refers to one of the oldest urban gardens of this program, [Can Mestres](#), which has 52 plots in a cultivating space of 6200 m². It also has a small farm with some animals to do activities with schools (Ajuntament de Barcelona 2023c). An external organisation manages this project and includes older people as volunteers. Notably, after 25 years of developing this program, only 15 gardens have been created. This reduced amount of gardens demonstrates the limited support this activity has historically received from the local government.

[Pla Buits/Mans al Verd Program](#): This program, initially called Pla Buits [*Empty Program*], started in 2012 and is currently known as Mans al Verd [*Hands on Green*]. It is a municipal program that aims to revitalise vacant plots of land in the city through temporary leasing to projects promoted by public or private non-profit organisations. Vacant plots are given through public tender. Currently, [17 community gardens](#) cover a total surface of 11.105 m², divided into different garden sizes, from 90 m² ([Jardins de Lanzarote](#)) to 1880 m² ([Hort amb Gràcia](#)). In a survey by the City Council, 17% of the gardens in this program stated that they were not practising organic farming (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2022). There is no budget disclosure on this program nor further online explanation on how granting one of these plots takes place.

[Program Garden in Terraces](#) is a project that was created in 2016 by the Municipal Institute of People with Disabilities (MIPD). It uses the terraces of municipal buildings to develop rooftop gardens cultivated by organisations working with people with disabilities. Currently, there are nine roof-top gardens (plus another one on the ground, the Pedralbes one). They use hydroponic agriculture as a therapy and learning experience for neurodiverse people. They have support from a company that does the technical work in the garden and guides them on the cultivating tasks. The gardeners distribute the harvest, and the surplus is sent to the Food Bank (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2024).

Two Districts (namely Horta and Gracia) indirectly fund two community gardens (The [Market Garden](#) and [Bosc Turull](#), respectively) because they are connected to environmental municipal facilities (i.e.,

aules ambientals, in Catalan). In Bosc Turull, they also offer technical assistance to school gardens and community gardens. These facilities are managed externally through tenders.

2.2.1.4 Subsidies and grants

Different subsidies and grants have funded community gardens in Barcelona (see Table 3 for a summary):

[Green Roofs Contest under the Climate Program](#): Twice, Barcelona City Council’s Municipal Institute of Urban Landscape has convened a Green Roofs Contest, an initiative promoting the creation of new green roofs in the city. The competition’s ten winning projects received a 75% subsidy on the cost, up to a limit of €100,000 per roof. Most of the awarded projects both times included community roof-top gardens.

[Decidim Participative Budget](#): Participatory budgets are a participation process from which residents of Barcelona can present, define, prioritise, vote, and, ultimately, choose investment projects that Barcelona City Council will execute in each district. The process, which began on February 3, 2020, has 30 million euros from the municipal budget for residents to decide which projects they want to support. They have funded several community gardens.

Some additional public grants could potentially fund community gardens despite not focusing strictly on urban gardens (e.g., Community action grants or Impulsem el que fas, which funds social and solidarity economy projects, or Climate Plan, which funds projects combatting the climate emergency). Still, they have very rarely funded community gardens.

Additionally, community gardens that are part of public equipment have funds allocated to improve their functioning. This is the case of *El forat de la Vergonya* garden or the aforementioned *aules ambientals*.

Table 3: List of public funding sources that have funded and could fund food sharing gardens in Barcelona

Name of the program	City Council Department	Funding details	Has it previously funded food sharing gardens?
<u>Green Roofs Contest</u>	Municipal Institute of Urban Landscape is connected to the Ecological Transition Department.	The competition’s ten winning projects received a 75% subsidy on the cost, up to a limit of €100,000 per roof. This program has taken place twice with no official recurrence.	Yes
<u>Decidim Participative Budget</u>	Participation	The program has 30 million euros from the municipal budget for residents to decide which projects to invest.	Yes,

Community Action grants	Culture Department	Grants to fund projects that strengthen communities, enhance living conditions and foster social inclusion and cohesion. Each call has a budget with a maximum amount per project.	No
Impulsem el que fas grant	Social and solidarity economy	Grants to fund projects that boost the economy of the neighbourhoods. They can fund up to 80% of the project with a maximum of 40.000 euros.	No
Climate Plan grants	Ecological transition department	Grants to fund projects that combat the climate emergency. They can fund up to 80% of the project with a maximum of 80.000 euros.	No
General call for grants for district and city projects, activities and services	Most departments and all districts	Annual general grants to fund projects in districts and in the city. In 2024 there was a budget of 22.500.090,82 euros.	No

Source: Own elaboration

2.2.1.5 Social urban farm key projects

In Barcelona, there is a social urban farm on public land, [Can Calopa](#). In Can Calopa, a social and solidarity economy cooperative manages a project to produce organic wine. It is a social farming project that works with young and neurodiverse people. The wine is partially given to City Council events and partially sold. Can Calopa has a small wine shop that offers services to host small meetings or events.

2.2.1.6 Future projects

A potential game-changer project in the arena of community gardens in the city is the *Agrovallbona project*. It implies the transformation of the last agricultural land of Barcelona (6,5 ha) into an agroecological complex combining productive land with community gardens. This project would be located in one of the lowest-income areas of Barcelona, and it would become the city's most extensive community garden. If materialised, it could also become an exemplary project based on environmental justice principles. The Agrovallbona project, however, is a long-term project that will have to survive many political changes in the local government. The current first stage implies an innovative modification of the land status that would grant protection and ensure its agricultural use: from developable to non-developable land (Ajuntament de Barcelona 2023e). If materialised,

this change would become a unique and pioneering legislative landmark to expand and protect urban gardens worldwide.

2.2.2 Major policy changes or developments relevant for food sharing gardens

There have not been significant changes since the first urban agriculture program began in 1997. However, in recent years, and especially since the push from the program Empty Plots/Hands on Green in 2012, there has been a more explicit institutional discourse on expanding green infrastructure, including community gardens, and the multiplicity of benefits that these gardens imply (e.g., health, environmental, social). Also, new (though limited) ways of funding have emerged.

In recent years, there has also been a tendency to transition from a model of allotment gardens towards more community gardens. This has occurred through different pressing factors. On the one hand, the limitations of space have pushed the City Council to encourage community gardens. However, new organisations have also emerged, questioning the dominant model of community gardens for older people and demanding to expand the potential users of community gardens. As a community garden member explains:

“In 2015, when this garden was in the planning stage, different associations from this neighbourhood wrote a small manifesto criticising that this space only could be used by retired people... they suggested that it could be done differently. This manifesto led to a series of meetings within a self-organising process in which there was the proposal of a project: the project suggested the City Council transfer the space and the management role to an association that was created on purpose to be able to cultivate this space and enjoy this environment. [...] We entered in May 2019 [...] We are the first regulated community garden in Barcelona. Before, these gardens were aimed at people over 65. We are the exception. We have associates from 3 years to 90, with the whole age range.” (Interview 4)

2.3 The diversity of food sharing gardens

Food sharing gardens in Barcelona take many forms. The following variables can help differentiate them and understand their characteristics:

2.3.1 Allotments vs community gardens

Allotment gardens refer to the municipal program of the City Council that started in 1997, named [“The Urban Garden Network or municipal gardens for old people”](#). The main trait of this classification is that the gardens are divided into 25-40 m² individual plots, and the resulting harvest is individualised. There are 200 plots distributed in 15 gardens throughout the city. People older than 65 can apply to get a plot in these gardens for a maximum of 5 years. The plots are awarded by lottery among the older people who apply (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2023d). The users cannot continue participating in this program after this time. Still, the City Council generally informs them about other existing community gardens if they want to continue the gardening activity (Interview 1).

Also, the Districts can decide that some organisations can use these allotments to perform therapeutic activities for people with functional diversity. The sharing dimension of these gardens is low. Still, they are not entirely “private urban gardens”, as users may share some items (tools, seeds, knowledge, time...). As the City Council technician mentioned:

“[These are] small plots and each person has its own. It is more difficult for older people to share things, but they do share. After a while, we realised they shared more than we thought. [...] If it is a public garden, it is a community garden, even if the communitarian aspect varies [*in intensity*].” (Interviewee 1)

These garden allotments can be located on the ground or in pots, and access to them is always facilitated by the City Council, which is also the direct manager of the gardens (through the municipal Institute of Parks and Gardens). There is no allotment garden taking place on roofs.

On the other hand, communal plots are used in the rest of the municipal programs as well as in the autonomous initiatives whose model of community gardening is based on sharing a communal plot of land and sharing the harvest. These plots of land can be on the ground or roofs; the gardening can happen using pots or directly in the ground; the City Council can grant access to the plot, or it can be squatted; and its management can be done by an organisation hired by the City Council or self-managed.

2.3.2 On the ground or on top of roofs.

This second distinction between different community gardens refers to where the gardens are located. This distinction is relevant because of Barcelona’s lack of spaces that could become community gardens. In recent years, there has been an increasing trend to promote roof-top gardens to look for other ways to increase green in the city.

Some gardens can be located on the ground, like the [Pedralbes Monestry Garden](#), while others can be roof-top gardens, like the ones on the roofs of the headquarters of the Sants District or the headquarters of the social services building. These three gardens belong to the social services municipal program “[Gardens on Terrasses](#).” The food cultivated in either the ground or roof-top gardens can be located in the ground or in pots. Another example of therapeutic community gardens in pots on a roof-top is the project [Hort d'en Llurba](#), situated on the roof of the Municipal Institute of Health Assistance - Institut Municipal d’Assistència Sanitària (IMAS) - ruled by the Hospital del Mar. In this project, the community gardens become a relevant part of the healing process.

2.3.3 In the ground or in pots.

This distinction refers to the place where the plants are growing. In some gardens, the plants grow directly from the ground; in others, they grow from pots. This distinction is related to the lack of space for gardening (e.g., in many roof-top gardens, the only way to cultivate is in pots), but it is also associated with a potential external constraining factor, namely soil contamination. If the soil is contaminated on the ground (e.g., especially in areas with intensive industrial activity), the City Council provides pots to cultivate. An example of this type of garden is the [Clot Garden](#), one of the projects that won the Barcelona participative budgeting in 2021. Another example showing the diversity of possibilities is “[The Market Garden](#),” a community garden located on the roof of the

municipal market in the neighbourhood of *Vall d'Hebron* where the cultivation takes place in the ground.

2.3.4 Granted access by the City Council, granted access by an organisation or squatted

While in all the examples above -and most of the community gardens in the city- there is the existence of a granting permit from the City Council, there are other categories of community gardens regarding who gives access to the cultivated space. A second type of access is related to community gardens in which an organisation grants itself access to its members, other organisations, or the broader public. An example of this category is the gardens of the [Medicos Sin Fronteras NGO headquarters](#) in which they have a community garden cultivated by users of different organisations that produce food for the Food Bank or the roof-top organic garden of the organisation [Ca la Dona](#), opened to any feminist wanting to participate. Additionally, some groups have squatted the land and perform their activities aside from the City Council. Examples of these gardens are [El Refugi](#), [L'horta alliberada](#), [Ca La Trava](#), [Horts de la Madaleta](#) and the historic [community gardens of Can Masdeu](#), which have existed for more than 20 years. The squatted garden can take place on either private or public land. The temporality of these gardens is somewhat uncertain. It depends on the land's property regime, whether a different project (e.g., housing) competes for the same space, and on the public support that the squatted gardens can mobilise. These squatted community gardens are generally linked to social movements in the neighbourhoods, and their space is used as a meeting point for different organisations. Many of these squatted gardens have been evicted (especially those on private land when the owners eventually presented an alternative use of the space like the gardens *Horteres de Gracia*, *el Huerto del Xino*, or *Date Una Huerta*). When gardens have been threatened with eviction, the City Council has acted as a mediator (Interviewee 4).

However, not all squatted gardens end up with eviction. For example, the squatted garden [l'Hortet del forat](#) in public space became public infrastructure from the City Council. In this iconic case, the squatted garden was part of a wider neighbourhood struggle against post-Olympic land development plans from the beginning of the 2000s (Cordero, 2016). After the City Council tore down some buildings in a poor area of the Ribera neighbourhood, the neighbours started a struggle to stop the process of speculation. The neighbour pressure stopped a new process of zoning aimed at the Pou de la Figuera square, where the City Council wanted to build a car park. The neighbours renamed the square The Hole of Shame (due to the rubble from the torn buildings that stayed there for a while) and eventually started a community garden that kept the name. After a participatory process, the City Council negotiated with the neighbouring organisations. The *Casal de Barri Pou de la Figuera*, a public facility, and a nursery home were built. In Pou de la Figuera square, the agreement implied that a hard plaza would not be built, but instead, the ground would be sand, sports fields, and a fountain, and the community garden would be maintained. In December 2007, after the Casal management was assigned to a private company, the neighbours complained, the public tender was paralysed, and the equipment eventually became community-based based on a civic management model defined based on citizen participation. In September 2013, due to pressure from neighbourhood groups and associations, the City Council gave space management to a neighbourhood group currently legally responsible for interacting and managing the Casal (Cordero, 2016).

2.3.5 Managed directly by the City Council, managed by an organisation hired by the City Council, managed by a third party organisation or self-managed

As we mentioned at the beginning of this classification, the City Council can directly manage the gardens and the community, as in the [“Urban Garden Network”](#), or it can also grant the manager role to another organisation. This organisation can be an external organisation that gets paid by the City Council, or it can be a community-led organisation that, through an agreement, is granted the space and management role for a limited amount of time (usually two years) that can be extended. These community-led organisation gardens include (but are not limited to) the type of gardens found in programs such as Pla Buits and Mans al Verd. In cases such as [Pla i Armengol Garden](#), [Icaria Garden](#), the [Clot Garden](#), or the [Can Batlló Community Gardens](#), there is a general assembly to take the decisions affecting the garden and multiple commissions. Thus, they are self-managed. On the other hand, external organisations managing community gardens must always coordinate with the City Council technicians while providing agricultural technical advice (e.g., the private company providing technical expertise in the [“Gardens on Terraces”](#) program). Additionally, these external organisations can sometimes perform facilitation roles between the participants (e.g., the cooperative operating as a manager in [“The Market Garden”](#)). In the case of private community gardens, they can either be self-managed or grant the managing role to another organisation, like in the case of [Medicos Sin Fronteras](#). Lastly, squatted gardens are always self-managed. Generally, the City Council intervenes as a mediator when there is an eviction threat.

2.3.6 Permanently opened, partially opened, with a reserved use

Community gardens can have different degrees of openness to the rest of the neighbourhood or a larger part of society. In a few cases, they are always open to whoever wants to access them (e.g., [L’horta alliberada](#) or [L’hortet del forat](#)). In most cases, they are partially opened, meaning that the gardens are locked, that some people from the manager organisation have the key to open them, and they are opened as long as the managers are in the gardens. In private community gardens or places with an explicit therapeutic aim for a vulnerable collective, the gardens are not generally open to the rest of society. Their use is restricted except if they are showing the project to third parties whose aim is to know it (such as other projects, museums, schools, etc).

2.3.7 School gardens

Many schools that are part of the municipal program Escoles + Sostenibles have a garden as an educational tool for students. In Spring 2018, 355 school gardens were identified. While they are community gardens for the school community, they have been excluded from the fieldwork since their governance is very linked to the educational project of each school.

2.3.8 Social enterprise agricultural farms

Social enterprise urban farms are agricultural cooperative projects run by organisations whose primary aim is serving the collective and/or general interest rather than making a profit. In Barcelona, only one project falls into this category: Can Calopa.

2.4 Main social movements and community organisations operating in food sharing gardens

The main social movements and community-based organisations operating in the food sharing gardens in the city are related to the community gardens themselves. Each garden becomes a community with different levels of organisation and formality. In the case of squatted community gardens, the links to other social movements are more visible, especially neighbourhood-focused social movements or the squatted movement itself. Many people participating in other social movements are part of or visit these squatted gardens. In the case of gardens on public land, gardening organisations are created on purpose, often due to cooperation between different organisations, to sign an agreement with a District, get access to the garden, and have the right to manage it.

Some of the organisations managing community gardens are neighbourhood associations (including youth associations, schools, secondary schools, summer schools, family groups, women groups, and *castellers...*), hospitals or neighbourhood health centres, scout associations, special educational centres, immigrant centres, religious groups (i.e., *Caritas*), fab labs (i.e., small-scale workshop offering digital fabrication), among others.

Some not-for-profit community organisations are working on therapeutic uses and social inclusion in community gardens for people with disabilities, mental illnesses, or physical injuries, such ATRA, *Associació septimània*, *Fundació Hospital Sant Pere Claver*, *Coordinadora d'Entitats Pro Persones amb Discapacitat de Les Corts*, *Associació Centre d'Higiene Mental de Les Corts*, *Associació Catalana de Traumatismes Cranioencefàlics TRACE*, *Fundació Cardenal Vid al i Barraquer*, *Associació per a la Rehabilitació del Malalts Psíquic AREP*, *Associació Promotora de Serveis especials Atencions Terapèutiques ASPROSEAT*, *Fundació Els Tres Turons*.

The Food Bank receives the surplus from some of the community gardens in Barcelona and distributes it among its network.

2.4.1 Main private sector enterprises operating in the food sharing gardens

One of the key operators promoting community gardens in Barcelona is the [Tarpuna](#) Cooperative. It was founded in 2012 and currently manages ten community gardens in different Catalan municipalities, including one in Barcelona, and acts as a consultancy for municipalities on urban gardening. They also organise the Aplec de l'agricultura urbana, an (almost) annual Catalan gathering to exchange experiences between gardeners.

Many other private, not-for-profit organisations work with people with functional diversity (e.g., *Fundació tres turons*, *Fundació Hospital Sant Pere Claver* or *Fundació Cardenal Vid al i Barraquer*).

Lastly, the presence of private companies in the community gardens is minimal — only a few companies fund some community gardens in Barcelona. For example, La Caixa Foundation has funded at least a therapeutic community garden. Also, The Merkat Garden reported that a private company was enthusiastic about the project and donated the irrigation system for their garden.

Of these organisations, the cooperative Tarpuna is the only one slightly more active about external governance. It is part of the institutional-community network Agropolis and acts as an advocacy

group for City Councils to advance the model of community gardens within urban gardens. The rest do not participate in any other governance structure.

2.4.2 The relationship between different food sharing gardens' actors

Generally, the actors in the food sharing garden arena collaborate.

Regarding discourses, community gardening represents a commonplace rhetorical consensus concerning its benefits. The actors' discourses, framings, and aims mostly converge around this topic.

The main elements of the discourse relate to the power of gardens to build communities, to the benefits (physical and mental) they entail for participants, or the potential they have as a tool to foster social inclusion. For example, the gardens can be regarded as a tool to enact and prove functionally diverse people's social contributions. Part of the food these gardeners produce is directed towards the Food Bank, generating social value for the donors and the recipients. As an interviewee told us:

We also donate the food. Donation takes place regularly. They [*the Food Bank*] are passive actors who receive the food, and from there, they cook it and make disabled people take on this role of contributing to society. And that for us is very important. Because at the end of the day, people with disabilities deliver the quality food they produce while dignifying people who go to the social canteen with this quality food. (Interview 3)

Additionally, positive environmental values are mobilised in the urban garden discourse, especially their instrumental role in promoting agroecology in the city, contributing to greening, and combating the climate emergency. The Strategy of Urban Agriculture (2019) describes urban gardens' environmental and social benefits as follows:

Urban gardens provide a range of benefits and ecosystem services. Although they are located in an urbanised ecosystem, they can generate environmental improvement on the environment, with which they achieve, among others, the following effects:

- Increase biodiversity.
- Recover habitats damaged by construction.
- Exercise water and microclimatic regulation.
- Improve air quality.
- [...]

The benefits that gardens generate for citizens are multiple and varied, such as the following:

- Contribution to food and nutritional security.
- Environmental education and recovery of agricultural knowledge add value to food and the professionals working there.
- Promotion of recycling and utilisation.
- Promotion of collective work, participation, and commitment.
- Fostering social ties and intergenerational relationships.
- Resource generation and self-employment.
- Inclusion, health, and well-being of vulnerable groups. (SUA, 2019:29)

2.4.3 Coordination spaces for gardens

While the different gardens know about the other gardens in the city, their interactions and collaborations are minimal. Maintaining the gardens already involves much work, and there is always a need for more participation in the projects, so the participants are mainly focused on their projects, activities, and relations within their communities. However, they can collaborate with other gardens when collaborating is needed. Most of these collaborations have an instrumental motivation regarding access to gardening resources and/or specific demands to the local government. As an interviewee mentioned:

“Regarding resource management, we sum up voices because we need certain things in urban agriculture that are very difficult to achieve. If we act as a network, it's easier to put pressure on them and get them. For example, in most gardens, we make compost. However, we have a limitation: we lack carbon-rich material. Since we all have this same need, we try to lobby [the Department of] Urban Agriculture in the City Council because they generate much carbon-rich waste that they grind [*through pruning, for example*]. Getting them to give it to us would seem easy, but it is not so simple. Yes, this is something we all act as a network to lobby.” (Interviewee 2)

No specifically functioning community gardening network articulates the different community gardens in the city. Once a year, however, there is a gathering of urban agriculture organised by Tarpuna, which generally mobilises projects in Catalonia. As an exception, in 2021, they also mobilised projects from all over Spain. In these gatherings, the participants share their experiences and challenges. An interviewee explained what they did in the 2021 gathering:

“We shared our experiences. In the assembly, we discussed the problems urban gardens faced in Seville or Bilbao. Then, we chose a few topics of most concern and discussed them in working groups. And we ended up with some conclusions that someone wrote. We shared experiences and got to know gardens from different places in Spain.” (Interviewee 4).

Additionally, in Barcelona, there is a network such as [Agropolis](#), a public-community network launched by the Barcelona City Council, where some actors can meet and share the goal of collaborating to transform Barcelona's food system through the values of food sovereignty and agroecology. Some community gardening actors participate in this network and connect with a broader space with different actors concerned with transforming the food system (i.e., not only urban gardens). Only occasionally, though, in Agropolis there are sessions that only focus on urban gardens.

2.5 Main enablers and barriers to food sharing gardens

2.5.1 Main enablers to food sharing gardens

2.5.1.1 Considering community gardens in urban planning

A fundamental enabler for community gardens is considering them in urban planning developments. This consideration is increasingly happening, but there is still much room for improvement. While the City Council department working most directly on urban gardens has

developed some internal regulations and technical specifications for urban planners to take into account, often, the incorporation of criteria could be more straightforward among public servants (especially from different areas). As an interviewee told us:

“Just like when you put a dog area, an exercise area for older people, or a children's play area, a garden for gardening or community farming for older people has increasingly been considered in urban planning. While it should always be there, it is not always there. I mean that we need to remember it a lot, too. There is much ignorance. For example, we had to put in the technical specifications of gardening, what needs urban gardens have, and how we need to manage them. This has also been something that we have done from within [*from the City Council itself*]. We can share this technical specification with a district that has tendered a space to see the potential of an urban garden. These are small things that we are improving within the regulations.” (Interview 1).

2.5.1.2 Access to Funding

One of the main enablers for community gardening is access to a stable funding source. Community gardens entail different costs (some are variable, and some are structural), and the gardens need funding. Many get initial funding, or the City Council directly covers expenses to set up the spaces. Still, after that, the investment in gardens is generally very limited. Sometimes, community gardens propose specific projects for funding and receive support (e.g., setting up a community composting space), but generally, they organise fundraising activities to cover their expenses (Interviewee 4).

A way that works in three or four locations to have stable funding is being part of or linked to a municipal facility (i.e., an environmental learning space or a civic centre). Changing the official classification of urban gardens and considering them a specific type of municipal facility, similar to the consideration civic centres have, could be a way to gain basic and stable funding and potential stability. The very same City Council recognises this, that is to say, from all the areas, districts, and professional people involved (EAU, 2019). As an interviewee put it:

“To me, a garden is a municipal facility at the same level as a civic centre [...] They have regular activities and a functioning dynamic operating through a community. Therefore, what we are missing and what is being claimed, especially from the organisations, the districts themselves, and the City Council, is that it should be considered a municipal facility. I think that this is an opportunity we can have. I remember when we started doing the Silent Garden in Gracia. We said: “We are a civic centre, without walls.” In other words, these gardens are doing the same work as a civic centre because many organisations go there, and many activities take place, and they organise weekly activities, etc. There are some learnings from the community, but it is not considered a civic centre. The gardens remain as a different classification from what would be a municipal facility. [...] If it were considered a municipal facility, it would have a budget to manage it. It would be civic management or tender, but it would have a basic budget that they might have to complement.” (Interviewee 1)

2.5.1.3 Lack of enforcement of food safety regulation

In many community gardens, there is either a harvest or a harvest surplus sent to the Food Bank to distribute among its network. While in theory, the Catalan food safety regulations should be applied to any donated food, this is seldom enforced, and organic fresh food produced in the city is sent to

vulnerable families. This lack of enforcement actually benefits civil society organisations. A public servant explained that this regulation originally relates to cattle farming regulations that do not adjust to the reality of what is currently produced with urban gardens. As they explained it:

“Yes, in theory, we cannot donate the food. In other words, defined by the health regulations of the Generalitat, self-consumption refers to family consumption. Beyond the door of your house, that is, of your family, of your relatives, let's say cohabitants in the flat or the house, whatever, you could not give it away. Nor if there was an economic transaction. Therefore, a food bank would already be a place where it should be regulated. Because at the moment, all this urban agriculture is very new... And above all, it currently cannot be done because it could not be done before. In other words, it is a [regulation] package that existed within urban regulations targeting mainly livestock activities. Excrement needed to be removed from the city due to the risks of pollution and health problems. But urban agriculture is developing, [this regulation] should be reviewed. Urban agriculture uses vegetable compost. There is no risk. The only potential risk is the contamination of soils that may have been industrial in the centre of the city. Well, all this is a regulation that still needs to be adapted. The new *Urban Development Plan* is taking it into account.” (Interview 1)

In fact, the *Mans al Verd* regulation (see next section) explicitly says: “Urban gardens will allocate the entirety of their production for the gardener’s self-supply and/or to the free supply of food to vulnerable people, either directly or through the mediation of organisations working on social assistance” (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2020).

2.5.1.4 Technical support

Another enabler for community gardens is having staff fulfil the technical support role. In many cases, this role consists of organising the daily work, preparing the materials, distributing the tasks, guiding the participants, monitoring their tasks, and being available in case of doubts or misunderstandings. While this figure implies a cost for the City Council, it has emerged as remarkably important, especially in the gardens that are not self-managed. As one interviewee mentions:

“It works best when there is a real presence of technical people who are there and explain [the things to be done] to them and pay attention to what they do. [...] We are making sure that the gardens work well. This works well: their presence and accompaniment. Moreover, we have seen it. When this person has been present, production has grown. There have been excellent harvests, and everyone has been thrilled.” (Interviewee 3)

Moreover, it has been identified in many community gardens that there is a need for a role to facilitate relations and help deal with interpersonal conflicts.

2.5.1.5 Flexible participation

In some gardens, participation and involvement are enablers. Generally, these are the gardens working in communal plots but having staff. A technical person organises the work and guides the participants throughout the tasks. This availability also allows more flexibility from the participants because regardless of whether they are coming to the garden, someone will cover the work and increase the garden's openness to new participants. As an interviewee said:

“We are lucky to have many participants here. We offer a very flexible participation model. People agree to come one day a week, but since all the work is communal, it is not terrible for the garden if one day is missed. Therefore, people know that they can sign up and participate. [...] What makes so many people participate is that we have moved away from the garden model of plots that go out by lottery, which is how many municipal gardens work. There are 20 places where people have two or three years to be on that plot, and then they must leave. Registrations are open here throughout the year. Anyone can stop by and sign up on the spot and participate in the garden even that day. Moreover, this makes it easier for people to participate when available. And they start, and they stick. [...] Participants come a lot to participate here because they know that it is a model that is very much designed for people who are starting to garden. No previous experience is necessary because a technician always gives instructions on how to do the tasks that must be done that day. And then that also makes many people want to participate.” (Interviewee 2)

2.5.2 Main barriers to food sharing gardens

2.5.2.1 Access to cultivation spaces

The main barrier to expanding Barcelona community gardens is land access. Barcelona is a dense and compact city with few spaces on the ground to create community gardens. This barrier also affects the amount of food and the type of crops that can be cultivated in the community gardens. This means crops needing more space (e.g., extensive crops) are not generally found in urban community gardens.

The limited public spaces that potentially could be used for community gardening are directly competing with other social uses (e.g., schools and other social infrastructure), so while there is a generally favoured disposition to expand urban gardens, there is a case-by-case assessment approach by the City Council. This competition between different uses of the public/community spaces happens in gardens on the ground and roof-top gardens (e.g., competition between solar panels and community gardens).

Also, the public spaces hosting community gardens are often bound to temporal leases (i.e. some of them two years), which impedes them from planning their project mid-term properly and wraps the garden communities into a permanent situation of uncertainty about their future. As an interviewee puts it:

“Perhaps it can be seen as somewhat daring, but we demanded a ten-year lease [for the community garden]. At the association level, it is demonstrated that we can last four years for sure, and if we have been able to last four years, we could last for ten. [...] Why did we ask for ten years? Because the only way to think mid-term is to have a guarantee that you will be able to do it. In two years, often, you cannot even think of introducing a new crop. It would be very tight to see if you managed [*and learned how to cultivate that crop*].” (Interviewee 4)

Despite these limitations, and while space is a major barrier to advancing urban gardens in the city, it also provides a compelling reason to promote community gardens in urban agriculture programs rather than a more individualised model. As an interviewee puts it:

“A major obstacle is space limitation. The space in the Barcelona Metropolitan Area is very limited, and generally, there is more demand from potential participants than in most

projects. To manage this, the only alternative is to do it through community projects. The individual-person model is not viable due to space availability.” (Interviewee 1)

2.5.2.2 Funding and access to other resources

A second major barrier to community gardens is the minimal funds for these projects, both public and private. On the one hand, while slowly increasing, the City Council does not have a significant budget for this. As stated in the Urban Agriculture Strategy:

Most districts demand more resources to arrange spaces for community gardens. It is necessary to have a budget to support these initiatives (EAU, 2019:26).

On the other hand, very few private funds support these initiatives. As far as we know, a private company donated money to cover the cost of the irrigation system of one garden, and one therapeutic garden has some funding from *La Caixa Foundation*.

Meanwhile, community garden projects have some expenses, mainly related to material needs (i.e., gardening tools, seedlings, water irrigation system, compost bins...), and thus have a permanent need for external funding. While all of these projects have structural costs (e.g., water), which the City Council covers, many of these projects (except for the projects for older people, the therapeutic gardens, and the ones that hire managers) need to devise ways to fundraise these costs. Sometimes, these activities become donations by the participants, self-raising activities, or merchandising. They grant some funding for the project, but overall, the community projects tend to be in a stage of somewhat precarity. As a gardener interviewee put it:

“We need tools to be replaced, and the irrigation system needs to be replaced. Even if we buy the greenhouse, sometimes sowing seeds does not always work, and we need to buy seedlings or more seeds. [...] In my opinion, we are tight. We could be doing much better. These nets [*nets to protect the crops against birds*] you can see all around us, we have been discussing for three years which type we should buy. We ended up buying the cheapest one; therefore, they did not last long. If we had a more stable funding source, these discussions would not exist, and I would not be here having irrigation problems. We would have a properly installed irrigation system. We are self-sufficient within the scarcity. We do what we can.” (Interview 4)

Sometimes, the same gardens are the ones that do not want to apply for public funds (and possibly even less if they were private funds). In self-organised community gardens, we find anti-subsidies positions that argue the need not to develop dependency relations with public institutions and, therefore, generally are positioned against receiving any funding from public institutions. As an interviewee explains:

“We debated whether or not to ask for a subsidy for the compost bins. There was a group [in our garden community] that did not want to because they did not consider subsidies as beneficial... In the end, the assembly accepted it because it was concrete, but then we agreed that we needed a more secure funding source if there were other projects like this [*the compost bins*]. So we decided that each participant would pay 10 euros/year.” (Interviewee 4)

Another barrier for the gardens is accessing additional resources needed for fully functioning gardens, such as electricity and carbon-rich organic matter. Electricity in gardens is needed to keep saved seeds in refrigerators. This way, gardens can reproduce their seeds and keep them for more extensive periods of time, safe from mice. As an interviewee told us:

“Another story was that from the first moment, after the 5,000 euros we spent on seedlings, it was clear that we had to save our seeds. Thus, we designed the garden to select several plants to get their seeds. We created the seed bank, and finally, we bought a greenhouse. But the seeds ended up being eaten by the mice. We did not have a specific refrigerator to store them. That is why we are demanding an electricity outlet.” (Interview 4)

“To make community compost, we need to put everything green there, but the brown [*matter*], which would be the branches from pruning, we are not allowed to put it there. And, besides, if we did it ourselves, we would have to chip it. Wood chipping it by hand, which we have already tried to do, is complicated. Of course, we bought ourselves a light wood chipper and got light for a few hours a week from the gardener's shed. But we managed to do that ourselves after much struggle.” (Interview 4)

2.5.2.3 Contaminated soils

Another barrier encountered in many projects is the existence of contaminated soil. In some parts of Barcelona, especially the districts with a strong industrial past (i.e., Sant Martí, Ciutat Vella, Sant Andreu, Sants), it is not possible to cultivate community organic farming on the ground. The City Council has increasingly found cases of soil contamination in potential gardens. When there is a risk of contaminated soils, the City Council requests a soil analysis. If positive, they set “cultivation tables” until they can find the funds to decontaminate the ground soil (i.e., remove the contaminated soil and bring new soil into the space). According to a City Council technician, this decontamination - performed by the Catalan Waste Agency - is costly.

“Now, we have a stable budget to arrange empty plots, put up a fence, and do some soil analytics. If we say: “This soil cannot be used,” we need to seal it and then put some cultivation tables until we have funds to decontaminate it. Decontaminating, as the Catalan Waste Agency does it- is costly. We are working with universities to explore other decontaminating ways [...]. Meanwhile, “it is winter”. We empty and remove the soil and put in new soil. But, of course, the soil structure takes many years to get stable... Soil contamination is a barrier on ground soil.” (Interview 1)

2.5.2.4 The climate emergency

The climate emergency is increasingly affecting community gardens in Barcelona. Increased temperatures, long summers, and water scarcity are some of the specific barriers that gardeners encounter. Many gardeners are part of vulnerable communities, and heat exposure during long hours is a threat they might need to avoid. As an interviewee puts it:

“Another important challenge is the climate crisis. Participating in a garden is increasingly hostile. During summertime, gardening is tough because while we are open to working with the public in general, the groups that participate the most in our garden are older people.

They are retired people, and participating on sweltering days is difficult for them. We are shifting to a model in which we do maintenance work during the summer: July and August. We do a minimalist planting. The participants are lucky that the crops grown in those months are very productive. Therefore, in a plot of peppers, there are lots of peppers. There is no need to plant five plots.

We try to have only half the garden planted in the summer to reduce this workload in the hottest months. But unfortunately, summer is getting longer and longer. And it is still October, and we were still hot here last week. That will make doing community gardens quite difficult because the work in the garden will be arduous for four or five months every year. Related to this, there is also a lack of water, which unfortunately will be worse. And in many cases, urban agriculture is identified as a consumer of water, which means that we are sometimes cut off from access to water". (Interviewee 2)

In recent years, water scarcity and increasing temperatures have emerged as two barriers to the functioning of the community gardens in Barcelona. The drought that Barcelona is experiencing due to the climate emergency has forced the City Council to apply drought measures in gardens by increasing efficiency and minimising water use. As an interviewee from the City Council Parks and Gardens department said:

"Water is and will be an increasing limiting factor. [...] What we stopped was surface irrigation. That is to say, we took away the hoses and gave them watering cans. To water only with the right amount of water. [We did this with] the elderly gardeners. For the people in the rest of the community gardens, in principle, most of them already had drip irrigation systems installed. If you do not have drip irrigation, the garden will not last. It is not feasible. Another issue would be that the irrigation system works, meaning there are no leaks. Everything related to saving water, minimising the use of water, and using rainwater, we need to improve a lot because we are currently watering with tap water, and this is a mortal sin". (Interviewee 1)

This interviewee also points out that more resources might need to be invested in developing better systems to catch and recycle rainwater or greywater and reduce the use of tap water, especially in light of the climate crisis. The water scarcity and the problems it entails, and the need to look for additional water sources are also mentioned by another interviewee who works in a garden:

"Access to water is what we have lacked the most here this summer. We lacked it so much that we no longer planned to plant the whole garden for the summer because we already knew there would be a lack of water. Even so, regarding what we planted, we had trouble keeping the plants alive because there was a lack of water. They [The City Council] lowered water pressure, the water did not arrive, and we could not irrigate. And I think this is something that affects all gardens. Most municipal gardens are irrigated with tap water. It is a costly resource. It would be very beneficial to get additional water sources for urban agriculture." (Interviewee 2)

2.5.2.5 Staff and technical advice on agriculture and collective decision-making

Having a technician to share agricultural knowledge, guide them on the different agricultural tasks, or support them has been repeatedly identified as an element of improving community gardens

(EAU, 2019). While the municipal program with older people involves five technicians, this is not enough to cover the demand. Additionally, while technical advice with agricultural knowledge, a technician profile with facilitation skills has also been identified, as many times, some basic norms of functioning need to be agreed and the community dynamics involve opposing visions, different interests and/or the emergence of conflicts that need to be addressed. While agricultural technicians sometimes play this social facilitation role, or some organisations seek this specific technical advice elsewhere, a need to cover this role has been identified in documents and interviews to enhance participation and reduce internal conflicts. As an interview put it:

“A community reality is not always so communal. [Imagine] we have a tree, and it is a tree for everyone. When we harvest, we will have some fruits to share. Well, this does not happen. There are no fruits because some people go first to harvest green fruits, so the neighbour takes them before. We need to work on this, but we do not have anyone [*professionally*] working on it. How do you prepare an assembly? How does it work? How do we make decisions? How do later work on issues, by committees or others? This work needs to happen.” (Interviewee 1)

Having more staff would also ensure better attention to vulnerable groups to ensure they receive enough support.

2.5.2.6 Individualised culture

A major barrier to boosting participation in these projects is the inertia of the individualised culture and its clashes with community dynamics and community projects. This individualised culture promotes the appropriation and privatisation of collective spaces or collective food production. The idea of the right to individual plots/tools/production is widely spread, and some people need to adjust their expectations when joining a community garden. As one interviewee puts it:

A barrier to participation is the lack of a culture of the common good and community functioning, that is to say, mine, mine, mine. “This is mine. This is my home. I put a lock on it”. Of course, working in common and for a community project goes against this external current that tells you that you have everything private, that everyone has a washing machine iron, and that you do not share it with your neighbours or anyone. That is why many people first say: “Oh, I want a plot in a garden.” “Well, no. Do you want to work in a garden? You will have a community plot.” “Huh?”. (Interviewee 4)

2.5.2.7 Participant involvement

Another barrier affecting community gardens, especially those with a self-organised governance structure, is the varying degree of participant involvement. This barrier is emphasised due to the consequences of overwork and overresponsibility that this entails for the rest of the participants. As an interviewee put it:

“At the level of participation, something we do not have in our consciousness is the community. It looks great as a word. It is great to talk about it, but when it comes to day-to-day life, the responsibility that the community entails, and how you get involved to make it work.... Oh, now we are not so much into it, are we?” (Interviewee 4)

While the aforementioned individualised culture could influence this other barrier, it is also important to bear in mind that the diversity of issues influencing this limited involvement extends beyond this aspect (e.g., people with care workloads have less time to participate).

2.5.2.8 Lack of Government Coherence

An additional and related barrier to the access to space for cultivation would be the limited coordination between different areas of the City Council (e.g., between the gardens department and the urbanist technicians in each district or between any area that develops urban gardens and the urbanists). Considering these urbanists' recommendations would be convenient when creating new community gardens. This consideration could improve the stability of community gardens. As stated in the Urban Agriculture Strategy:

There is a lack of coordination with the district's land planning services. It would be important to include planning recommendations when planning new gardens or managing potential spaces to develop agricultural activities. [...] Urban agriculture and environmental projects are not considered cross-cutting issues. This creates a very segmented vision of projects and a lack of alignment when working on common goals. (UAS, 2019, p.24)

2.5.2.9 Urban food production selling ban

The ban on selling food produced within the urban area is a barrier to expanding community gardens, according to some participants (see below section 2.5.3). Currently, this ban implies that all produce must be aimed at self-consumption, and this is something that some community gardens agree. However, other community gardens, especially the ones where more vulnerable profiles participate, regard this ban as a barrier. Lifting this ban would imply self-generating income that could either be spent on the project itself, directly (through the economic benefit produced by the sales), or indirectly (by the funding saved by the City Council that could fund more projects) funding other organisations doing similar work. It could even create employment for some (vulnerable) social groups. As an interviewee explained:

Obviously, if there were an economic benefit, it would benefit us. [*Not being able to sell the harvest*] is one of the things that slows it down. [*At the City Council*] we have this guaranteed budget because these gardens are a municipal investment. But of course, [*the selling ban*] is clearly a brake when it comes to expanding, for example. If the ban were lifted, on the one hand, [*the neuro-diverse participant organisations*] would be able to self-finance themselves. Then, in the longer term, this could become a model for organisations in this sector to earn money. For example, this could be a source of employment for special work centres. It would be fantastic. Perhaps it would not be like that for most of those who participate because it is a profile they cannot work on, but there is a part that they probably could. Or a part that we have not reached yet and that could certainly benefit. (Interview 3)

2.5.2.10 Unregulated areas

The selling ban is also impeding the flourishing of innovative practices in urban agriculture, which could create economic value for the gardeners, such as producing organic sprouts in cultivation tables. This ban, added to the actual lack of regulation whatsoever of the type of agriculture that

can occur in roof gardens, creates a situation of uncertainty about what can and cannot be done in these potential cultivation spaces. As an interviewee mentioned:

“All the agriculture that can be done on roofs should be regulated - this is the one that is *a-legal*, not illegal, that is, there is no regulation. In other words, there is no waste here. Well, if you do hydroponics, there is water, but we recycle it most of the time. But in principle, there are no regulations that prevent you from making sprouts with a cultivation table, and all this must be regulated. We also have much work to do at the regulatory level.” (Interview 1)

2.5.3 Conflicting interests among different actors involved in food sharing gardens

One of the main aspects creating a conflict of interest among actors is the ban on food commercialisation in the urban area. While this ban constitutes a barrier for some urban gardeners (e.g., the projects where vulnerable groups use gardens for therapeutic goals that could create value and more return to the rest of society), other community-based groups consider it an undesirable regulation. In these groups, in which they already have tensions due to different visions of the garden (namely more productivist vs. more holistic), this change could potentially introduce more tensions if some of the gardeners considered it an opportunity to advance the productivist vision.

Importantly, changing this ban would imply changing the Metropolitan General Plan (MGP), which would, at the same time, imply broader political debates on the many topics this plan regulates. Therefore, although the demand to lift this ban is recurrent and stated by many actors, including the City Council, the change will only be possible once the MGP is wholly modified. This conflict of interest has not affected the relationships between the groups of actors.

On the other hand, while a Catalan regulation forbids food donations from gardens, the lack of enforcement allows donations to reach vulnerable populations through the city's food bank. Moreover, this lack of enforcement benefits not only food receivers who get healthy, fresh, and mostly organic vegetables but also the gardeners who are part of vulnerable communities (i.e., people with disabilities) for whom providing food for others represents a meaningful action. For these gardener communities, being able to contribute to society is a crucial element in their lives. Surplus donations, thus, emerge as an essential aspect of their activities.

Lastly, the community model is increasingly shaping what food sharing gardens are in Barcelona. The leading food sharing garden programs and public funding favour community gardening models. For instance, even when a gardener spends the maximum number of years in an allotment, they are redirected towards a community garden.

2.6 The influence of the cultural and socio-ecological context on food sharing gardens

2.6.1 Features of the city's cultural context particularly relevant for food sharing gardens

Barcelona has a long tradition of social movements and collective organising (Sánchez Belando, 2015). The many different organisations within the city's neighbourhoods create valuable social

capital. These movements have influenced Barcelona's urbanism through specific demands or more direct decision-making processes (García-Ramon and Albet, 2000). The strength of social movements and, more specifically, autonomous movements in Barcelona has helped expand community and squatted gardens during the last decade, linking and reinforcing the garden communities with different neighbourhood organisations. At the same time, the influence of the autonomous movements also affects the internal funding policies of food sharing gardens, as public funding is often negatively regarded as institutional whitewashing and an independent DIY culture, though economically precarious, prevails.

Moreover, since culture is typically expressed through the patterns and nature of interpersonal relationships, the community gardening model could not likely be implemented in all cultural contexts (i.e., it might not likely be implemented in Nordic European countries). The community gardening model is related to a more collectivistic society in which individuals tend to rely on existing social networks compared with individualistic societies, where people tend to continuously choose when to form and abandon bonds (Schug, Yuki, & Maddux, 2010).

Also, Barcelona's urban form conditions the type of food sharing gardens that can be created. The city's compactness and density, the lack of vacant land, and the typical architectural constructions (i.e., city blocks) favour the emergence of terrace gardens.

2.6.2 Features of the city's socio-political context particularly relevant for food sharing gardens

During the aftermath of the 2008 economic crisis, when austerity approaches dominated the political arena, the *Convergència i Unió* government developed the Empty Plots Plan to promote temporary initiatives in vacant plots in 2012. This plan was an example of the emergence of what some authors call temporary urbanism (e.g., Ferreri, 2021) or the politics of meanwhile spaces (Cruz Gallach & Martínez Moreno, 2016). They refer to allocating a budget to small-scale projects and communities that temporally organise activities in vacant spaces. Though imposing short-term precarity for communities, this plan also simultaneously allowed a change in the dominant model of community gardens for older people. New user profiles forming communities started populating the arena of community gardens facilitated by the City Council.

Since *Barcelona en Comú* (*BComú*) won the local government in 2015, food sharing gardens have multiplied for two electoral cycles. During this period, the Empty Plots /Hands on Green Plan has been strengthened, and the gardens aimed for therapeutical purposes have multiplied. Moreover, the City Council published the Urban Agriculture Strategy in 2019 and the 2030 Healthy and Sustainable Food Strategy in 2022. The publication of these two strategies indicates the will to grant more centrality and support to urban agriculture in general and community gardens in particular.

While the public sector is a major social actor granting (very limited) funding for community gardens, the spread of publicly funded community gardens has also promoted the emergence of additional gardens on private premises. However, overall, there is not much private investment in community gardens in the city.

During the last electoral cycles, there have still been garden evictions on private properties. However, after participative processes promoted by the *BComú* government, some historic

squatted gardens (i.e., *el forat de la vergonya*) have also become community-managed public facilities.

The current PSC government (starting in June 2023) seems to hold a continuist approach regarding urban gardens.

2.6.3 Features of the city's ecological and climatic context particularly relevant for food sharing gardens

The climate emergency is highly and increasingly relevant for food sharing gardens in Barcelona. It is a relevant barrier in many gardens, especially during the year's hottest months. The persistent drought affecting Catalonia and, hence, the city of Barcelona also affects food sharing gardens, and water scarcity is becoming an element that will increasingly affect the type of crops that will be able to be cultivated as well as the parts of the garden that will be able to be cultivated. Likewise, as temperatures increase and summer hot periods expand, it will also increase the difficulties of vulnerable people to participate (especially older people).

Moreover, soil contamination from the city's industrial past is essential to food sharing gardens. The presence of contaminated soils involves enormous consequences for both the public sector and the food sharing initiatives. The former will either decontaminate the soil or provide alternative soil and infrastructure for cultivation. Either way, the cost of setting up the garden will significantly increase. On the other hand, the latter will likely experience a significant delay in their project to have the space set for cultivation and will have to wait for the responses given by the public sector to the problem or ask for a relocation (which might also imply a long wait).

2.7 Conclusions

The data gathered in this report shows some of the most relevant aspects shaping the governance of food sharing gardens in Barcelona. We categorised the different types of food sharing gardens and the elements that can explain their diversity. We described the main regulations affecting these gardens. We identified the City Council's main areas involved with these gardens and the primary sources of public funds they receive. We also identified this activity's main barriers and enablers, identified the main conflicts of interest between actors, and analysed these elements considering their cultural, socio-political, and ecological contexts.

The findings show that despite favourable discourses and predispositions towards food sharing gardens, their presence and support are minimal. The lack of institutional coherence and coordination among the different areas dealing with food sharing gardens difficults their expansion and the dialogue with the stakeholders involved. The model of gardening that the City Council is increasingly prioritising is the community gardens. This model could increase the social and health benefits of food sharing gardens, increase social interactions among gardeners and improve their organisational skills. While advancing this model is also a valuable path to democratising access to gardens to a more significant part of the population, the amount of cultivating spaces (both on the ground and terraces) is still minimal compared to the size of the city and its population. Therefore, more space, institutional support, and private and public funding are needed to expand food sharing gardens in the city.

Moreover, while some community gardens are located in private enterprises, there is minor funding available from private sources to fund community gardens. One of the most striking findings is precisely the timid presence of the private sector on this topic. Involving this sector could become an opportunity to mobilise funds, expand gardens, and involve additional social groups.

We also identified a lack of enforcement of regulations affecting food sharing gardens. On the one hand, the lack of enforcement of food safety laws regarding food donations benefits food sharing gardens and the vulnerable groups receiving the food they produce. On the other hand, the underlying assumption behind the lack of enforcement of the plant health law is that all food sharing gardens practice organic farming. The lack of control mechanisms to verify the organic practices in food sharing gardens shows either naivety or indifference from the City Council regarding the potential consequences of pesticides for the people's health and the urban ecosystem's health.

The inexistence of a functioning community garden network also poses a difficulty for gardeners to coordinate among themselves. This network could identify common barriers and align their discourses and priorities. Thus, they miss the opportunity to become an organised entity and increase their influence on the local government and the rest of society.

2.8 Policy Recommendations

2.8.1 To City Council

- Increase available funding and resources:
 - Consider gardens as municipal facilities;
 - Create a program specifically for Community gardens;
 - Facilitate the engagement of the private sector with food sharing gardens;
 - Increase budgets for urban gardening in the City Council;
 - Create funding guidelines for community gardens with potential funding sources;
 - Facilitate additional resources (electricity, matter for compost),
 - Systematise the process of facilitating access to gardening materials and services (e.g., create official and accessible online forms to request electricity, wood chipper, carbon-rich material for compost making, etc.).
- Improve access to cultivating spaces.
- Enhance coordination within the City Council.
- Enforce urban garden guidelines.
- Increase technician support (both for agricultural knowledge and group facilitation)
- Create the role of Community Engagement Coordinator within the City Council to provide direct support for community gardens.
- Adapt to the climate emergency (e.g., create shades and water catcher systems).
- Find better ways to decontaminate soils.
- Create an advocacy structure for Community Gardens in the city.
- Create a public platform for centralising all information and communicating about community gardens
- Include urban agriculture in urban planning and regulation

- Review food safety regulations to include exceptions for donations of freshly produced vegetables.

2.8.2 To Food Sharing Gardens

- Increase flexibility in participation structures.
- Promote facilitation tools among participants.
- Consider applying to public or private funding.
- Create a stable network of community urban gardens.
- Improve communication.

2.8.3 To private sector

- Consider funding food sharing gardens.
- Create food sharing gardens in private premises.
- Partner with other organisations to manage food sharing gardens located in private premises.

3. Food Waste and Redistribution (FWR)

3.1 Introduction

Food waste redistribution is a complex phenomenon that usually refers to the use of food diverted from its original objective of alleviating food insecurity in those in need. However, it cannot be analyzed independently, as it interrelates and overlaps with other activities that aim solely at food waste prevention, food security, or food safety regulations, among other issues.

To properly understand the food waste and redistribution (FWR, hereinafter) system in Barcelona City, it is essential to understand the existence and coexistence of different types of initiatives/projects. They fall into different approaches, depending on whether food is considered surplus.

Figure 1 presents three approaches related to FWR initiatives:

- 1. Food loss and waste prevention:** These initiatives focus on reducing food loss and waste at its source, thereby preventing its generation through corrective measures. This approach is deemed the most preferable in the field of food loss and waste, as it offers significant environmental, economic, and social benefits. Actions and initiatives falling under this approach include "food loss and waste prevention plans" mandated by the Catalan Law for Food Waste Prevention (*Llei 3/2020 de Prevenció de Pèrdues i Malbaratament Alimentaris, LPPMA*) (Government of Catalonia, 2020), along with technologies like *Lean Path*, which employs smart scales to reduce food waste in the food service sector. Efforts at the Hospital Germans Trias i Pujol have also led to a decrease in food waste. Additionally, platforms like [P\(O\)MA](#) foster industrial symbiosis among agrifood companies, repurposing food waste as a resource for other food companies while creating new market channels. Also, encouraging "doggy bags" in restaurants to take leftovers home aims to reduce post-consumption food waste.
- 2. Food surplus redistribution:** this approach provides a second opportunity for food intended for human consumption that does not reach its original consumer by distributing it to other consumers. This can take various forms, whether through economic transactions or acts of solidarity to enhance food security. Initiatives like [Too Good to Go](#) and "[Encantado de Comer](#)" utilize applications to sell surplus food from shops, restaurants, and bakeries at reduced prices. Otherwise, some initiatives redistribute food surplus through donations destined for people at risk of social exclusion to promote food security and the right to food. [Fundació Espigoladors](#) is one of these initiatives, which redistributes fruits and vegetables that are about to be lost in the fields or wasted in the warehouses of agrifood companies to social entities of food distribution. Community kitchens also utilize surplus food to feed those facing social exclusion. Additionally, Foodback collects surplus food from Barcelona's wholesale market, redirecting it to social entities aiding vulnerable populations. Further initiatives involve donating surplus food directly to those in need, exemplified by the "solidary fridge" concept, where individuals can donate and access surplus food freely. The

Espigadoras de Poble Sec exemplify grassroots efforts, organizing through WhatsApp to recover surplus food from local shops for redistribution within their community.

3. **Food redistribution, food security, and right to food:** this approach encompasses various initiatives to bolster food security and ensure the right to food. Unlike efforts focused solely on preventing food waste, these initiatives involve redistributing food that is still suitable for sale in shops.

One such initiative is "[El Gran Recapte](#)" (translated "The Great Recovery"), organized by the Food Bank. It involves collecting mainly dry or canned foods purchased by individuals at designated supermarkets and donating them to social entities before Christmas. Additionally, companies may donate food or funds to support social initiatives or food banks. Public procurement programs that purchase food for distribution to those at risk of social exclusion also align with this approach. Finally, there are schemes providing prepaid cards to individuals in vulnerable situations, enabling them to purchase food from specific shops or supermarket chains.

Figure 1 Three main different approaches to food redistribution. Source: Fundació Espigoladors

It is also essential to know the existence of a “**food waste hierarchy**”, shown in Figure 2. The food waste hierarchy outlines a prioritized approach to managing food waste, emphasizing prevention and reduction over disposal. It begins with prevention actions, then proceeds to the re-use of surplus food fit for human consumption, repurposing food unsuitable for humans as animal feed, recycling materials into high-value products (with partial degradation), nutrient recovery, energy generation, and finally, as the least favourable choice, food waste disposal. Therefore, it is crucial to consider that optimizing the food waste hierarchy would reduce food waste and, therefore, redistribute food waste. These complex dynamics must also be considered.

Thus, all the FWRs for human consumption are encompassed within prevention or re-use for human/animal consumption actions at the top of the hierarchy, while recycling, recovering, and disposal are considered wasting activities.

Figure 2 The food waste hierarchy. Source: Implementation of a food loss and waste prevention and reduction plan in agri-food companies: principles and guidelines, from the Catalan Government ([link](#))

3.2 Policies and Regulations

A complex and intricate normative landscape parallels the great diversity of actors involved in FWR in Barcelona. FSIs are affected by different legislative areas depending primarily on their type of activity.

Regulations and normative targets that may influence FWR activities belong to different fields, such as FLW prevention, food redistribution/donation, food safety, food and agriculture, waste, and animal feed. Thus, the different regulations and normative targets identified at the international, European, national, Catalan, and municipal levels are classified according to the previously presented fields.

3.2.1 International level:

Internationally, the most noteworthy aspect in reducing food loss and waste is not regulations per se, but primarily non-binding international agreements that focus very specifically on promoting the prevention of this issue (Table 1).

Table 1 Policies and regulations related to food waste redistribution activities at the international level.

FLW Prevention	SDG 12.3 Champions: initiative “10x20x30”, SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) Food waste hierarchy
Redistribution/ food donation	Food waste hierarchy
Food safety	
Food and agriculture	Milan Urban Food Policy Pact: food waste prevention objective
Waste	
Animal feed	

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations, 2015):

Among them, SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) has objective 2.2: “By 2030, end all forms of malnutrition, including achieving, by 2025, the internationally agreed targets on stunting and wasting in children under five years of age, and address the nutritional needs of adolescent girls, pregnant and lactating women and older persons.” This provides an incentive, even in local territories within so-called “developed countries,” to better feed the most disadvantaged and vulnerable parts of our society. This momentum could serve as a framework to encourage increased food donations by various entities committed to the SDGs in Barcelona.

Another SDG worth highlighting is SDG 12.3, which focuses on reducing food loss and waste: “By 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses.” Therefore, by combining both objectives, it can be deduced that a feasible approach to addressing both is through better utilization of surplus food that cannot be prevented by redirecting it towards human consumption, which is the ultimate destination for which it was produced.

To inspire ambition, mobilize action, and accelerate progress toward achieving SDG Target 12.3 by 2030, [the Champions 12.3](#) initiative has been created. It is defined as a high-profile, voluntary coalition of leaders from governments, businesses, international organizations, research institutions, and civil society dedicated to facilitating the achievement of these objectives for reducing food waste and losses by 2030. Within Champions 12.3 lies the initiative called “[10x20x30](#)”, which brings together 10+ of the world’s largest food retailers and providers, each engaging at least 20 suppliers to halve food loss and waste by 2030.

The effort catalyzes a “whole chain” approach to fighting food loss and waste and supports upstream food loss and waste reduction. Each food retailer, provider, and supplier has committed to the “Target-Measure-Act” approach: set a target of reducing food loss and waste in their operations by 50%, measure and publish their food loss and waste inventories, and reduce their

waste. This initiative can serve as a driving force, as some of these entities participating in 10x20x30 are located in the city of Barcelona, encouraging other major food companies in the sector to join these commitments, thus fostering an environment of increased food flows for final consumption by people.

Milan Urban Food Policy Pact

The Milan Urban Food Policy Pact, an international protocol to tackle food-related issues at the urban level, is to be adopted by as many world cities as possible. The city of Barcelona is among the signatory cities. This protocol comprises a Framework for Action listing 37 recommended actions, clustered into six categories. One of these categories relates to “food waste,” which includes the following four recommended actions:

- Convene food system actors to assess and monitor food loss and waste reduction at all stages of the city-region food supply chain (including production, processing, packaging, safe food preparation, presentation and handling, re-use and recycling) and ensure holistic planning and design, transparency, accountability, and policy integration.
- Raise awareness of food loss and waste through targeted events and campaigns; identify focal points such as educational institutions, community markets, company shops, and other solidarity or circular economy initiatives.
- Collaborate with the private sector, research, educational, and community-based organizations to develop and review municipal policies and regulations to prevent waste or safely recover food.
- Save food by facilitating recovery and redistribution for human consumption of safe and nutritious foods, if applicable, that are at risk of being lost, discarded, or wasted from production, manufacturing, retail, catering, wholesale, and hospitality.

This makes it an ideal framework for promoting and incentivizing through utilizing food surplus through FWR, serving as an element of demand for the general public to continue working and promoting this framework in Barcelona.

3.2.2 European level:

A wide variety of topics affect the issue of food loss and waste in a cross-cutting manner (Table 2). Unlike at the international level, it mainly concerns mandatory regulations for the different member states, many of which will be transposed into national legislation. Thus, regulations directly or indirectly impact FWR at the local level.

Table 2 Policies and regulations related to food waste redistribution activities at the European level.

FLW Prevention	Commission Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/1597 of 3 May 2019 Food waste reduction targets
Redistribution/ food donation	European Union aid programs: ESF+ Basic Material Assistance Program
Food safety	Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law

Food and agriculture	Application of the Common Food Policy in Spain (Fruit and vegetable removal program) The Farm to Fork Strategy European Green Deal Directive 2019/633 on unfair trading practices in business-to-business relationships in the agricultural and food supply chain Regulation No 543/2011 in respect of the fruit and vegetables and processed fruit and vegetables sectors New circular economy action plan (CEAP) Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on the provision of food information to consumers
Waste	European Union Directive 2018/851 amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste Framework SANDACH (link)
Animal feed	Regulation (EC) No 767/2009: on the marketing and use of feed (link)

European Union Directive 2018/851 Amending Directive 2008/98/EC On Waste Framework (European Union, 2018)

Regarding waste and food waste and losses, the most relevant current regulation at the European Union level is the European Union Directive 2018/851 amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste Framework. Within this Directive, there is already an indicative target for reducing food waste at the Union level of 30% by 2025 and 50% by 2030. Among the main measures to address this issue is that Member States will promote food donation and other means of redistribution for human consumption, prioritizing human consumption over animal feed and transformation into non-food products.

The European Green Deal (European Parliament, 2020)

In point 61, The European Green Deal reinforces the commitment to halve food waste in the European Union by 2030.

Commission Delegated Decision (Eu) 2019/1597 Of 3 May 2019 (European Parliament and of the Council of the European Union, 2019)

Another regulation that advances in the direction set by the 2018 Directive is the Commission Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/1597 of 3 May 2019, which establishes a common methodology and minimum quality requirements for the uniform measurement of levels of food waste. This regulation implies that each Member State must report data on food waste throughout the agri-

food chain, thereby strengthening the involvement of public authorities in diagnosing and addressing this issue, with one of the main solutions being the reuse for human consumption.

The Farm to Fork Strategy (European Commission, 2020b)

The Farm to Fork Strategy indicated that in 2022, the first data on food waste and losses in all European Union Member States would be published, serving as the baseline for binding reduction targets on this issue. This has already represented, and is expected to be, a significant support for public policies aimed at minimizing food loss and waste (FLW), thus allowing for greater momentum in food waste reduction (FWR) actions.

Directive 2019/633 On Unfair Trading Practices In Business-To-Business Relationships In The Agricultural And Food Supply Chain (European Parliament and of the Council of the European Union, 2019)

The Directive 2019/633 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on unfair trading practices in business-to-business relationships in the agricultural and food supply chain (European Parliament and of the Council of the European Union, 2019) could have an indirect impact on FWR, as it aims to combat practices that manifestly depart from good commercial conduct and has an impact on the food losses and waste generated in the distribution sector but ultimately affect the primary sector. In this way, the food surpluses generated in the distribution sector may need new avenues for minimization, such as food redistribution, instead of returning them to the primary sector.

Regulation No 543/2011 (...) In Respect of The Fruit And Vegetables And Processed Fruit And Vegetables Sectors (European Commission, 2011)

In a similar line to the previous one, there is Commission implementing regulation No 543/2011 of 7 June 2011 laying down detailed rules for the application of Council Regulation (EC) No 1234/2007 in respect of the fruit and vegetables and processed fruit and vegetables sectors, which establishes quality requirements that all fruits and vegetables in the European Union must meet, although it also sets out specific commercial requirements for some fruits and vegetables. Among these requirements are some terms that are more purely aesthetic than quality-related in terms of whether they are considered edible, which generate food surpluses that need to be reduced, mainly through processes of distributing these foods for human consumption.

Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 (...) Laying Down the General Principles And Requirements Of Food Law (European Parliament and of the Council, 2002)

An example of regulation that directly affects food exchange processes is Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety. Additionally, there is an indirect formula that this regulation significantly affects, as it determines the very concept of food. The current definition outlined in this regulation excludes as “food” all agricultural products that have not been harvested. For this reason, all fruits and vegetables left in the field without being harvested, perfectly edible by humans, are not considered food. Thus, these discards fall outside the system of monitoring and reducing food waste mandated by the European Union through the regulations mentioned above,

rendering these flows “invisible” and reducing their possibilities of minimization, for example, through distribution to people.

European Commission Delegated Regulation (Eu) 2021/1374 Of 12 April 2021 (European Commission, 2021a)

A direct impact of such European regulations on FWR can also be clearly seen in the European Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/1374 of 12 April 2021, where it is indicated that food business operators engaged in retail activities may freeze meat to redistribute it for food donation, provided they meet a series of conditions.

New Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) (European Commission, 2020a)

Within the new paradigm known as the Circular Economy, the European Commission adopted the New Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) in March 2020. It is one of the main building blocks of the European Green Deal, Europe’s new agenda for sustainable growth. Within these actions, the commitment to reducing the issue of food waste in the European Union is reinforced. As part of the Circular Economy Action Plan, the Commission has adopted EU food donation guidelines (European Commission, 2017) to facilitate the recovery and redistribution of safe, edible food to those in need. The EU food donation guidelines seek to:

- facilitate compliance of providers and recipients of surplus food with relevant requirements in the EU regulatory framework (e.g., food safety, food hygiene, traceability, liability, VAT, etc.).
- promote common interpretation by regulatory authorities in the EU Member States of EU rules applying to the redistribution of surplus food.

Building on the EU food donation guidelines, In June 2020, **guidance on food safety management systems for food retail activities** was published, including food donations, aiming to support food business operators, such as butchers, bakeries, groceries and ice-cream shops, including food banks and other charities, in their implementation of EU rules to ensure the safe production of food sold to the consumer. The guidance further facilitates food donation by recommending some simple additional good hygiene practices that ensure the safe redistribution of surplus food.

A regulatory matter affecting particular products is **Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/2258 of 9 September 2022** (European Commission, 2022), which amended Annex III to Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 and now requires that eggs be delivered to the consumer within a maximum time limit of 28 days of laying.

A less normative and voluntary approach is the **EU Code of Conduct on Responsible Food Business and Marketing Practices** (European Commission, 2021b), which is a voluntary code of conduct for responsible food businesses to contribute to the transformation of the food systems in which they operate within their sphere of influence. Its main objectives and measures are preventing and reducing food losses and waste. Thus, through this voluntary code of conduct, there would be the possibility for new food businesses to join, expanding the possibilities for food redistribution as a means to minimize this issue.

3.2.3 European Union Aid Programs

At the level of European Union aid programs, [the ESF+](#) is configured as the main instrument of the European Union to invest in people and implement the European Pillar of Social Rights and achieve the objectives set out in the 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda. For the programming period 2021-2027, it merges the European Social Fund (ESF), the Youth Employment Initiative (YEI), and the Fund for European Aid to the Most Deprived (FEAD), to achieve one of the three priorities of the ESF+ which is social inclusion and the fight against poverty and social exclusion, prioritizing measures to reduce and prevent child poverty.

The ESF+ Basic Material Assistance Program replaces the **former [European Aid Fund for the Most Deprived \(FEAD\) program](#)**. One of the main novelties of this Program is the replacement of the system of food and hygiene product supply with a system of provision of shopping cards or redeemable vouchers that allow beneficiary families to purchase fresh food and those products they consider most necessary in their particular situation. This change significantly affects current aid entities, as they will be limited in the food assistance they receive and instead will be provided with debit cards that they can mainly redeem at large supermarket chains.

3.2.4 Spanish level

In this case, it concerns mandatory regulations throughout the Spanish state that, like European regulations, cover a wide range of topics. Indeed, some of these regulations are transpositions of the mentioned European ones. It even includes the draft of a future national law that may significantly impact the field of food loss and waste once approved.

Table 3 Policies and regulations related to food waste redistribution activities at the Spanish level.

FLW Prevention	Draft Law on the Prevention of Food Losses and Waste
Redistribution/ food donation	Patronage Law (Royal Decree-Law 6/2023, Of December 19)
Food safety	Law 17/2011, of 5 th July, of food safety and nutrition (Transposed law of Europe) Real Decreto 1086/2020, de 9 de diciembre, por el que se regulan y flexibilizan determinadas condiciones de aplicación de las disposiciones de la Unión Europea en materia de higiene de la producción y comercialización de los productos alimenticios
Food and agriculture	Law 12/2013, of August 2, on measures to improve the functioning of the food supply chain. Application of the Common Food Policy in Spain (Fruit and vegetable removal program)
Waste	Law 7/2022, of April 8, on waste and contaminate soils for a circular economy
Animal feed	Law 17/2011, of 5 th July, of food safety and nutrition (Transposed law of Europe)

Law 7/2022, Of April 8, On Waste and Contaminated Soils For A Circular Economy (Jefatura del Estado, 2022)

At the national scale, the reform of the 2018 European Directive has been transposed into Spanish legislation through Law 7/2022, of April 8, on waste and contaminated soils for a circular economy. This law also sets reduction targets for food loss and waste. Thus, its main novelty, compared to the indications of the Sustainable Development Goals, is the reduction of 20% in the production and supply stages by the year 2030. A percentage that was not clearly defined by SDG 12.3, as the 50% reduction target was set for the retail and consumption stages. This national law also develops the need to specifically incorporate food waste into waste prevention plans, thus promoting the implementation of such plans that can ultimately both prevent waste and facilitate the provision of new food for donation or use as food for people.

Patronage Law (Royal Decree-Law 6/2023, Of December 19) (Jefatura del Estado, 2023)

A state law reform with a significant impact on food receiving entities and also on economic donations is the reform of the Patronage Law (Royal Decree-Law 6/2023, of December 19), which improves the tax incentive regime to promote micro-patronage, continuous donation, and increase private investment participation. The modification, made by Decree-Law, increases incentives for both individuals and legal entities, as well as non-residents.

One of the main novelties is the increase in the tax deduction amount in the income tax return. Until December 31, 2023, the first 150 euros deducted 80%, and beyond this amount, 35%. From now on:

- Up to 250 euros of donation: deduction of 80%
- Beyond 250 euros, the donated amount will be deducted at 40%
- Recurrent donations, such as those from subscribers to many food-receiving entities that maintain or increase the amount, will be deducted at 45% (provided that a donation has been made in the two previous years and at least for the same amount).

The reform of the Patronage Law also modifies the advantages regarding the corporate tax: one-time donations are deducted 35% and recurrent ones, 40%. With the changes, it now stands as follows:

- 40% for one-time donations
- 50% for recurrent donations (provided that a donation has been made in the two previous years and at least for the same amount).

Furthermore, donations of goods and the temporary transfer of use of movable or immovable property, made without consideration, will also be deductible.

To qualify for the deductions, donations must be destined for non-profit entities for the purposes of this law. To do so, they must meet the requirements outlined in the Law.

Law 12/2013, Of August 2, On Measures to Improve The Functioning Of The Food Supply Chain (Jefatura del Estado, 2014)

Indirectly, Law 12/2013, of August 2, on measures to improve the functioning of the food supply chain, could impact the flow of food at the local level. Indeed, this law analyses the current situation

of the value chain, highlighting clear asymmetries in bargaining power that can lead, and sometimes do lead, to a lack of transparency in price formation and potentially unfair commercial practices, as well as practices contrary to competition that distort the market and have a negative effect on the competitiveness of the entire agri-food sector. These asymmetries sometimes lead to food losses at points in the chain that do not cause this problem, such as the production sector, which ultimately suffers in the form of volumes of food lost due to abusive practices in later stages of the chain. This law aims to reduce the current rates of food loss and generated waste, which could facilitate formulas for donating these surpluses.

Law On The Prevention Of Food Losses And Waste (Gobierno de España, 2021)

It's also worth highlighting the impact of future state laws currently being processed, especially the case of the Draft Law on the Prevention of Food Losses and Waste. Thus, while the definitive text will be approved hopefully shortly, a core part of the law lies in the obligation for all food companies at every stage of the chain to have a food loss and waste prevention plan. Within this plan, the primary reference will be the hierarchy in surplus food management, which prioritizes the minimization of this issue by preventing and donating these surplus foods. This would increase the flow of food for donation.

Law 17/2011, of 5th July, of food safety and nutrition (Jefatura del Estado, 2011)

This law represents establishing a common basic legal framework applicable to all activities encompassing food safety and promoting healthy nutritional and lifestyle habits. It sets out the requirements that must be met for food and feed to be considered safe for placement on the market while also ensuring that this safety extends to consumers with special dietary needs. In order to achieve this, the principles underlying the new conception of food safety have been taken into account, such as risk analysis, traceability, and the precautionary principle, which are fundamental elements for ensuring consumer safety.

Royal Decree 1086/2020, of December 9, regulating and flexibilizing certain conditions for the implementation of European Union provisions on the hygiene of food production and marketing, and regulating activities excluded from its scope of application (Ministerio de la Presidencia, 2020).

This regulation aims to address three distinct situations. Firstly, it establishes exceptions or adaptations to flexibilize the requirements outlined in various European regulations on health safety and hygiene for certain types of establishments and products. Secondly, it regulates activities excluded from the scope of application of these regulations. Moreover, it finally establishes measures that contribute to correctly implementing European Union regulations in Spain.

3.2.5 Catalan level

At the regional level, in Catalonia, a similar effect occurs as with the national and European frameworks: many regulations stem from adapting Spanish legislation to the Catalan territory. Within this group of regulations and norms, there is great diversity in topics and regulatory tools, from regional laws to assistance protocols/guides.

Table 4 Policies and regulations related to food waste redistribution activities at Catalan level.

FLW Prevention	Ley 3/2020 – LPPMA, Law for food waste prevention – (regulation still under development) Som de Profit- communication campaign (Catalan Waste Agency) Catalan government FLW prevention strategy Guidelines for FLW prevention plans
Redistribution/ food donation	Catalan Food Safety Agency- Food donation protocols
Food safety	Transposed law of Spain
Food and agriculture	PEAC – (Public funding with a specific line for FLW prevention) Catalan Bioeconomy Strategy 2030 Law 16/2017, 1st August, of Climate Change
Waste	SANDACH (Transposed law of Spain) Waste and Resource Prevention and Management Programme of Catalonia (PRECAT20)
Animal feed	

Llei 3/2020 De Prevenció De Pèrdues I Malbaratament Alimentaris (Government of Catalonia, 2020)

At Catalan level, the Llei 3/2020 de Prevenció de Pèrdues I Malbaratament Alimentaris (LPPMA, Law for food waste prevention) was approved by the Catalan parliament. The LPPMA, which received inputs from several coordinated FSIs (see previous section), aims to reduce 50% of food waste in Catalunya by 2030. It prioritizes reducing losses and food waste over redistributing surpluses and covers the whole food chain. In the case of food producers and distributors, as well as formal FSIs, the LPPMA makes it mandatory to have a food waste prevention plan. This plan is a comprehensive document where businesses quantify food waste and analyze its causes to identify critical points and develop strategies for reducing food waste. The plan is considered an exercise of accountability and requires a compromise from food-related actors to reduce food waste. The law also establishes a hierarchy of priorities about what to do with food waste, in which redistribution for human consumption is favoured when possible, with animal consumption and composting as secondary options. Finally, the law The LPPMA also introduces a series of obligations for restaurants and catering businesses. In short, they must allow costumers to take away food not consumed at no additional cost and inform their clients about this option. Moreover, they must accept containers brought by the costumer to that end, or alternatively provide either reusable or compostable containers that are apt for storing food. As for the public administration, the LPPMA poses the obligation to include clauses for food waste prevention in all public contracts for food sourcing. However, the regulation of the law is still pending and will surely impact the agents with its specific application of the mentioned principles.

Strategic Food Plan of Catalonia 2021-2026 (DACC) (Generalitat de Catalunya, n.d.-b)

The Catalan government has developed a strategic food plan for the 2021-2026 period. Among other objectives, it wants to use the food supply chain as a tool to fight climate change, and one of the lines of work is preventing food loss and waste through different initiatives.

Catalan Food Council (DARP, 2023)

This council aims to be the forum of participation and collaboration among the different agents of the Catalan agri-food system and lay the foundations for a new national food policy based on local food production and sustainable management of the environment.

Som De Profit (ARC) (L'Agència de Residus de Catalunya, n.d.)

To avoid food waste, which in Catalonia amounts to discarding 260,000 tonnes of edible food each year, the Catalan Waste Agency created this communication campaign of citizen awareness. This campaign offers various tools, including a travelling exhibition, a workshop for schools, and a web space ([link](#)).

Aprofitem els Aliments – **Food Loss and Waste prevention strategy (DACC)** (Generalitat de Catalunya, n.d.-a)

To reduce food loss and waste in Catalonia, the Agriculture Department developed this strategy to coordinate the different agents in the food supply chain to reach the related SDGs (reducing food waste by 50%). They do that by: generating knowledge, through food loss and waste diagnoses in different sectors and, participating in European projects; and by organizing different activities to raise awareness and improve the technical abilities of the different agents.

Protocols and clarifications by the Catalan Food Safety Agency (ACSA)

The Catalan Food Safety Agency has developed several guidelines, protocols, and clarifications to make it as simple as possible to understand the mechanisms of food donation and incentivize it. On its website, you can access summarized information on how and who to donate to. Additionally, there is general food safety information, such as clarifications on best-before dates and expiration dates, among others.

Among these guides, notable ones include the guide titled "[Guia per a la implantació d'un pla de prevenció i reducció de les pèrdues i el malbaratament alimentari a les empreses agroalimentàries](#)" (Guide for the implementation of a plan for the prevention and reduction of food losses and waste in agri-food companies) and the "[Guia per a la prevenció del malbaratament alimentari als menjadors escolars](#)" (Guide for the prevention of food waste in school canteens). But especially noteworthy is the guide called "Requisits de seguretat alimentaria en la donació d'aliments" (Food Safety Requirements in Food Donation). This document has been developed to compile and harmonize the food safety and hygiene requirements that must be met by social entities involved in various forms of food donation. It is intended to serve as a guide for all educators who, in terms of food safety, must train and advise social entities participating in donations. The first part includes the general requirements of food hygiene that volunteers handling food must meet, the facilities of the social entity, and food products. Information on the various hazards that can affect food and

how to control them completes this general section. Specific requirements are also included according to a series of possible phases involved in food donation:

- Transport of food.
- Reception.
- Storage.
- Delivery.
- Handling.

Catalan Bioeconomy Strategy

This strategy was approved in 2022, incorporating the mandate and knowledge from the European bioeconomy strategy and the constraints from Law 3/2020 (see above) to promote the growth and sustainable development of the Catalan economy by encouraging the production of biological resources and local and renewable processes (Departament d’Acció Climàtica, 2021).

Roadmap for the circular economy in Catalonia

This Roadmap (to 2030) defines the mission, vision, strategic objectives and operational objectives to accelerate the transition of the country towards a more circular and fair economy that maximizes the value of resources and acts as a lever for transformation in a framework of collaboration between key actors. It includes a 2024-2026 action plan with 15 lines of action and 80 specific actions to improve circularity in Catalonia (Generalitat de Catalunya, n.d.-b).

Law 16/2017, 1st August, of Climate Change

Article 14, states that the measures adopted in agriculture and livestock farming should aim to reduce vulnerability, greenhouse gas emissions, food waste, and resource consumption (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2017).

Royal Decree 210/2018, of 6 April, approving the Waste and Resource Prevention and Management Programme of Catalonia (PRECAT20)

Article 6 states the objectives of the PRECAT 2020. One of them being: Reduce by 50% in weight food waste in the areas of retail distribution, catering, meal service, and domestic environments compared to the 2010 baseline (Ministerio de Agricultura y Pesca, 2018)

3.2.6 At the municipal level

The diversity of topics is much more limited at the local level than at the European, national, and regional levels, as it focuses particularly on "food and agriculture" and "waste" topics. Therefore, no specific themes address the issue of food loss and waste in general, nor the realm of donations specifically. Within this territorial context, the development of plans and strategies predominates.

Table 5 Policies and regulations related to food waste redistribution activities at municipal level.

FLW Prevention	
Redistribution/ food donation	
Food safety	

Food and agriculture	Barcelona strategy of healthy and sustainable alimentation (EASSB2030) Barcelona Metropolitan Region Food Charter (CARMB) Food procurement Instruction OCAS (Joint Office for Sustainable Alimentation)
Waste	Pla de Residu Zero 2021-2027 (PRZ, Zero Waste Plan 2021-2027) The Climate plan
Animal feed	

Municipal grants:

- Convocatòria general de subvencions [General Grants]
- Enfortim l'economia social i solidària [Grants for social and solidarity economy projects]
- Justícia Global
- Impulsem el que fas
- Subvencions pel clima

Barcelona 2030 strategy of healthy and sustainable food (EASSB2030)

The Barcelona 2030 strategy of healthy and sustainable food (EASSB2030) gathers all the activities by the Barcelona municipality related to sustainable food. This document was developed in a participative way with the collaboration of many civil society entities and sets a roadmap until 2030, with nine strategic objectives and 265 actions to accomplish by that year. It is concretized in a yearly action plan that records all the activities already performed by the municipality in the previous year and the new activities that will start in the following year, with numerical indicators. The strategy wants to guarantee access to healthy and sustainable food, if possible, from a community perspective, fostering grassroots initiatives. And specifically, regarding food waste, one of the nine strategic objectives of the strategy is to prevent food loss and waste through promoting innovative methods to redistribute or channel them (more specific actions by the Barcelona municipality are listed in the INITIATIVES & ACTORS section).

One of the main achievements of the municipality, which is included as part of the food strategy, is the creation of **food procurement instruction**. This document is a guideline on how the municipality should buy food or draft tenders for food activities, including organic, seasonal, and local products. Interestingly, it includes the obligation for tenders with more than ten employees to have a food waste prevention plan.

[Zero Waste Plan 2021-2027](#) (Ajuntament de Barcelona, n.d.-b)

Other relevant regulations include the Zero Waste Plan 2021-2027 Barcelona (ZWP) developed by the Waste Management Department, which is a tool for facing strategic challenges and goals around waste prevention and management. The guiding document was created after a participatory process in which 184 participants from several council departments and relevant organizations held 16 meetings and seven workshops. The ZWP includes food waste prevention as one of its key strategic lines, which is divided into two areas. The first tackles prevention and food waste by: integrating it as a concern in all caterings organized by the council; fostering it among big

commercial actors, schools, restaurants, and catering businesses, and in municipal infrastructures; raising public awareness; and fostering responsible food consumption. The second area concerns the redistribution of food surpluses and seeks to promote redistributing efforts among big food waste generators. This series of strategic goals have their own implementation plans and are articulated into projects.

[The Climate Plan \(Ajuntament de Barcelona, n.d.-c\)](#)

The **Climate Plan**, under the environment department, is a municipality's strategy that aims to fight against climate change by aligning municipal actions and directives. Specifically, regarding food waste redistribution, this strategy aims to fight against food wastage by promoting integrated management of the food production cycle to prevent food wastage, establishing compulsory mechanisms and circuits for reusing surplus food, studying possible rebates on waste taxes, carrying out communication campaigns for the consumer public, promoting the reprocessing kitchen, etc. (2020).

Still at the local level, but this time under the competence of the Department of social services, the **Alimenta project** proposes a new social food model that prioritizes the recipients' dignity and empowerment. The project combines the classic function of providing food to those in need with integrative actions that boost people's autonomy and concerns about healthy and sustainable food. This is achieved, for instance, through community cooking workshops addressing food recovery. Alimenta is structured around three main goals: providing an efficient and equitable response to food poverty, advancing towards a less charitable ("assistencialist") model, and promoting public-private collaborations. Each of these goals shapes an axis of action. The first axis, *Aliments amb sentit* (Food with meaning), seeks to work on securing resources to cover the demand for social food in the city of Barcelona. The second axis is *Espais Alimenta* (Alimenta spaces), which seeks to develop and manage spaces in collaboration with FSIs. These spaces are used for traditional redistribution operations and social functions like the previously mentioned cooking workshops. The third axis, *Impuls de projectes de col·laboració public social* (Promotion of public-private collaboration projects), aims to guarantee access to fresh and healthy produce to people experiencing vulnerability. They do so by fostering the involvement and commitment of the private sector, mainly through the use of the *Tarjeta Barcelona Solidària*. This card is accepted in various businesses in the city where the subsidies of aid recipients are deposited.

[Barcelona Metropolitan Region Food Charter \(CARMB\) \(Barcelona Demà, 2020\)](#)

Barcelona is the biggest and most influential city of broader regions, the Barcelona Metropolitan Area (AMB) and the Barcelona Metropolitan Region, which include 36 and 160 municipalities, respectively. In order to coordinate policies and actions, the Barcelona Metropolitan Strategic Plan was developed. A specific commitment to food was developed through the Barcelona Metropolitan Region Food Charter (CARMB), which aims to, among other things, prevent food waste in school canteens.

[Joint Office for Sustainable Alimentation](#)

Food competence is shared among different administrations and historically has not been considered as a municipal one. Lately, cities have understood the need to build a more sustainable food system and that they can be the spearhead of the most progressive policies. Nevertheless, to

boost the projects they want to implement, it is necessary to coordinate efforts with other administrative levels that, in several cases, have the legislative capacity. To try to solve to some extent this issue, the OCAS (Joint Office for Sustainable Alimentation) was created to be a space of collaboration between the different administrations that rule over the Barcelona Metropolitan Area, in this case, the Barcelona Municipality, and the Climate Action Department of the Catalan government (DACC). They want to transform the food supply chain by introducing the concept of sustainable food into the projects developed under municipal (EASSB2030), supramunicipal (CARMB), and national (Strategic Food Plan of Catalonia 2021-2026) guidance.

3.2.7 Municipal subsidies calls

Finally, the Barcelona municipality calls for several subsidies that can be awarded to FWR projects. The *Impulsem el que fas* call has a specific line devoted to projects or social initiatives that contribute to a change in the consumption model and a healthy, sustainable, and fair food supply chain. Moreover, in the general call for subsidies and the *Justicia Global, Enfortim l'economia social i solidària*, and the *Subvencions pel clima* calls, sustainable food (including FWR) is one of the areas of action.

3.3 Initiatives and Actors

FWR is a vast and heterogeneous dimension of urban food sharing that encompasses many different practices, conceptual dimensions and political visions in the city of Barcelona. As such, it is hard to establish a categorization of the actors involved in FWR in the city that can give us a comprehensive understanding of the matter.

In order to deal with this diversity, we propose a typology based on the type of activities related to FWR that different actors carry out, keeping in mind that those categories are highly correlated, and some projects could arguably fall into more than one of them:

3.3.1 Channelling food surplus:

This activity connects food donors/sellers with social distribution entities, who distribute the food to their end users. This activity is predominantly performed by big organizations acting as suppliers of smaller FSIs that distribute food on the ground to their end consumers. The origin of the food is mixed, with a certain amount of recovered produce mostly from wholesale and retail, but also with direct purchase. They fulfil a complex logistical role and enable the connection between big donors and smaller organizations, acting as a hinge of the food redistribution sector.

Some organizations that recover and channel food about to be lost or wasted could be: [Fundació Espigoladors](#), which goes to the production fields with volunteers that harvest edible fruits and vegetables that, for some reason (mostly price frictions and aesthetic requirements), the farmer will not sell, and channels it to other FWR organizations; other organizations, such as [Fundació Àurea](#), [Nutrició sense fronteres](#) or [Pont Alimentari](#) focus on diverting food that would be wasted or lost otherwise, and channels it to organizations that distribute it to end users (see point 2).

Other organizations, such as [Fundació Banc dels Aliments](#), channel surplus food and buy it for donations. This practice, though obviously outside the scope of FWR, clearly affects it by shaping the needs and constraints of the entities.

3.3.2 Distributing food surplus to end users:

The entities in this category channel food from other entities, particulars, or buy food surpluses to distribute to end users, mainly people in vulnerable situations. This group includes very big and institutionalized organizations as well as grassroots, self-organized ones. There are several categories of actors doing this type of activities:

One subgroup within this category is formed by big charities with local food distribution centres, mostly in areas with high poverty levels. Most of the produce that they redistribute is sourced by FSIs channeling surplus. The most popular of these organizations are probably [Creu Roja](#) (the local branch of the Red Cross), or [Càritas](#) through its [DISA](#) (Distribució Solidària d'Aliments, Charitable Food Distribution in English) centres.

A second subcategory includes smaller formal organizations that, still under a charitable approach, are grounded in particular neighbourhoods, usually around a religious or cultural centre. Many of these also receive produce from channelling FSIs, but they also have their own local connections that allow them to recover food or receive donations that are later redistributed. To receive food from channeling FSIs, they must fulfil specific requirements of the capacity of handling food under food safety legislation, non-discrimination during the food distribution, and being a non-lucrative organization, among others.

A third group would comprise more informal local food networks based on horizontality and mutual aid. These informal groups, connected to the neighbourhoods' social fabric, are sourced by recovering food and occasional donations from local businesses and markets. They do different actions, such as food collection from neighbours or local shops, or “skipping/urban gleaning” as it is sometimes called. Many of these emerged and thrived during the COVID-19 pandemic, some of which later disappeared or have become hardly active. Some of these entities would be:

- [Xarxa d'aliments Can Baró](#)
- [Xarxa suport Roquetes](#)
- [Xarxa de suport Trinitat Nova](#)
- [Xarxa de suport Porta](#)
- [Xarxa d'aliments Guinardó](#)
- [Xarxa de suport Carmel](#)
- [Xarxa d'aliments Vallcarca](#)
- [Banc Expropiat / Assemblea Gràcia](#)
- [Comitè Revolucionari d'aliments Poble Sec](#)
- [Xarxa d'habitatge de l'Esquerra Eixample](#)
- [Xarxa d'aliments de Sants](#)
- [Xarxa d'aliments del Poble Nou](#)
- La Comuna – Sagrada Família
- [Xarxa d'aliments Verneda i La Pau](#)
- [Xarxa Suport Mutu La Sagrera](#)
- [Xarxa d'aliments La Prosperitat](#)
- [Can Batlló](#)
- [De veí a veí](#)

- [Bon veí, bon profit \(Barceloneta\)](#)
- [Rebost Solidari de Gràcia](#)

In some cases, grassroots entities have also established solidarity fridges in civic centres, youth centres and other public spaces. This is a more private way of redistributing food that seeks to respect the intimacy of the recipients. Some of these solidarity fridges in Barcelona are:

- [Nevera Solidària Casal Ateneu L'Harmonia Sant Andreu](#), Barcelona,
- [Nevera Solidària Espai Antoni Miró Peris](#), Barcelona
- [Nevera Solidària al Casal Joves del Queix](#), Barcelona
- [Nevera Solidària Sagrada Família](#), Barcelona.

Finally, there is a last group that diverges from the previous one and is formed by companies (for-profit) that act primarily as a digital intermediary of food redistribution. This food does not necessarily correspond with food about to be wasted but can be another market channel for shops. They do not donate the food but sell it at a discounted price to everyone who wants to buy it, not only people in need. One of the most popular companies of this kind is [Too Good to go](#), which enables food establishments to sell leftover food at the end of the day through the app rather than discarding it. Some critics argue that platforms like this may inadvertently encourage overproduction by providing a safety net for food establishments to sell their excess food, usually from low nutritional value and quality (Interview 1). [Encantado de comerte](#) would be a very similar company. [Talkual](#) is a different initiative that buys surplus and “ugly” food from Spanish farmers and distributes it to particulars and companies at a discounted price.

3.3.3 Transforming surpluses:

Entities in this category transform/process food surpluses to donate to people in vulnerable situations or sell them to anyone wanting to buy them.

First, the Barcelona municipality provides vulnerable citizens access to cooked meals through different channels. The “[Menjadors socials](#)” are canteens where people in need can access food, and there are also meals delivered to people’s homes, and accompanied meals, aimed at fighting against loneliness. However, through the [Alimenta project](#), the municipality aims to transform the model into a more empowering one by creating a new model on canteens as a space where the users can cook the redistributed food themselves and share the meal with other users while creating a network. Also, the [Cuina de Barri de Sant Antoni](#) is a community kitchen located in a public facility where they do urban gleaning, this is asking from food close to expiration to shops and restaurants in the neighbourhood, and the users cook together the food.

Then, several social organizations have kitchens where they cook the produce before its redistribution. The origin of the food is very diverse, depending on the nature of the FSI. For example, [Fundació Formació i Treball](#) has canteens and channels the cooked meals to smaller organizations to be distributed.

Another subgroup comprises FSIs that recover surplus food, transform the recovered produce, and sell it later. [Sobres Mestres](#) is a catering service that partially uses surplus food, and Fundació Formació i Treball has a ready meal shop in Sant Antoni ([D’ins a casa](#)), that sells partially recovered food to the general public and is also thought as a work insertion centre. E.I. [Es Im-perfect](#), from Fundació Espigoladors, commercializes a line of spreads and jams made of surplus fruits and

vegetables that can be found in several supermarkets. They also produce spreads and jams to donate in specific projects, such as: “**conservas que cuidan**” and [La Marga](#) (see in awareness raising).

3.3.4 Preventing food waste:

Some initiatives mainly work to prevent food waste as its main objective, reducing it from its source, so there is no food surplus to redistribute or donate. [Fundació Espigoladors](#) offers consultancy to companies or organizations to prevent food waste. Similarly, [Pont Alimentari](#) and [Fundació Rezero](#) help companies and administrations prevent food waste. For example, through their project [Remenja'mmm](#), they promote the use of doggy bags in restaurants to prevent food waste. [Te lo sirvo verde](#) is a consultancy company that helps food restoration companies reduce food waste. They have also produced guidelines to help implement food waste prevention plans in the school canteens.

Lobbying is also effective for preventing food losses and waste and fostering the redistribution of surpluses. Several entities that work with food waste devote efforts to lobbying political parties and administrations, especially during the preparation of the Catalan Law for food waste prevention (2020) and lately during the process of drafting the forthcoming Spanish law. Some of the organization with incidence in Barcelona that were involved in these activities were: [Fundació Espigoladors](#), [Fundació Rezero](#), [Plataforma Aprofitem els Aliments \(PAA\)](#), among many others.

The municipality of Barcelona promotes several projects to prevent food waste. The [Projecte Alimenta](#) from the Barcelona Municipality (see also previous chapter), while its main objective is to ensure that people in risk have adequate food, through its open kitchens and workshops, empowers the users while promoting the importance of reducing food waste. Like [Projecte Alimenta](#), every time more food security projects include objectives apart from giving food to users, making it more transversal.

Apart from that, the municipality of Barcelona is involved in multiple networks that, amongst other objectives, include food waste reduction and redistribution as a goal. At the international level, Barcelona participates in the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact, C40, and Eurocities. Also, Barcelona signed the Good Food Declaration and promoted the Barcelona Challenge for Good Food and Climate, tools in which halving food waste by 2030 was a city commitment. Finally, at a national level, Barcelona is part of the [Network of Municipalities for Agroecology](#) (Red de Municipios por la Agroecologia). Belonging to these networks is an additional boost to the propositive intentions of the municipality.

3.3.5 Awareness raising:

This category includes mostly cultural and pedagogical activities aiming at changing people's behaviour towards food waste prevention. These initiatives are mostly occasional and aim to disseminate good practices and educate and raise awareness about food waste. This category entails the work of many different organizations, from different sizes and typologies. [Plataforma Aprofitem els Aliments](#) (PAA) organizes popular meals cooked with recovered food. [Fundació Espigoladors](#) does many types of activities to educate and raise awareness on the FLW issue among many different publics, from more open activities to raise awareness to the citizens in general, to many educative projects in different types of schools, to teach in university courses, etc. [Pont Alimentari](#), for instance, has produced several guides to make food waste and its associated problems known, sharing advice for reducing and reusing it.

Finally, from the municipality Barcelona, several projects also want to raise awareness on the topic of food waste and its associated injustices. [Ens ho mengem tot](#) is an educational program where the students from primary schools analyze all the wastage they produce and links it with concepts such as local food or carbon footprint. [Alimenta't amb seny](#) is a more generic alimentation program but includes food waste topics. Additionally, several smaller education programs also want to make a difference. For example, [La Marga](#) (included in transforming surpluses) is an integral program, where volunteers and the sent for transformation glean oranges from orange trees in Barcelona. This program, though, clearly focuses on raising awareness, retuning the jam made with orange from each neighbourhood to its place of origin and sharing it with the social entities and doing several workshops to explain the process and the food waste issue.

3.3.6 Summary

Barcelona has a rich and extensive network of agents and projects aiming at Food Waste Redistribution, from big non-profit entities that operate following conventional logics to small neighbourhood initiatives to try to create disruptive practices apart from the system. Assembling all those initiatives together is a big challenge, but it is one that can surely produce great benefits from the citizenship of Barcelona and the environment.

As seen in this chapter, the categorization of the initiatives is very complex, as several actions could fall into more than one category due to their transversality and their vocation of solving multiple problems. Specially for the **Preventing food waste** and **Awareness rising** categories, we found that most of the activities focused on other objectives also incorporated, at least tangentially, this advocacy for the fight against food waste and redistribution to those in need.

Not only actions are transversal, but several actors can be found doing actions in several categories. [Fundació Espigoladors](#), [Fundació Rezero](#), [Pont Alimentari](#), [Plataforma Aprofitem els Aliments](#) (PAA) but especially the municipality of Barcelona is, as it should be, a holistic agent that works in multiple fronts and plays a key role in the system.

3.4 Main Enablers and Barriers of Food Waste Redistribution

The following part of the document describes some of the barriers and enablers that Food waste and redistribution initiatives face when executing their activities.

Considering the great diversity of initiatives that actively contribute to FWR in Barcelona, it is complex to determine a series of general obstacles and enablers. The type of activity that FSIs carry out, their nature (public / private / community; formal / informal), their political vision and the scale at which they operate all determine specific barriers that they face and elements that facilitate their activities. Apart from the research in the previous chapters, interviews with specific FSIs and public administration have been conducted to deepen the difficulties and enablers they see in their day-to-day activities. The selection of initiatives covered virtually all the categories outlined in the Actors section and different typologies of FSI and public actors. Moreover, patterns pointing to partially or totally shared obstacles and enablers across categories and types of FSIs and the public administration will be identified.

3.4.1 Main enablers of food waste redistribution

3.4.1.1 FSIs sector consolidation

As the different organizations and administrations point out, Barcelona is a very diverse city with a rich environment of organizations that work in the FWR and have similar or related objectives. Even from the administration's point of view, it becomes clear that the role of FSIs is crucial to enable efficient food redistribution in the city as they carry most of the responsibility in terms of FWR. The organizations are numerous and diverse in size and typology, resulting in a diverse and symbiotic network of entities. As the FSIs point out, the sector has gradually consolidated, which is both the cause and consequence of the coordination between the agents (including public administration), which has been increasing and improving, allowing for more co-created projects benefiting each organization's expertise. As some interviewee mentioned:

“The administration has provided more resources in terms of infrastructure, refrigerators, and vans. I mean, there has been a slow articulation but perhaps we are more advanced than in other places.” (Interviewee 1)

“In recent years there have been social kitchens. We supply them with food, and what they do is prepare meals and distribute them to the organisations.” (interviewee 5)

3.4.1.2 Increase trained professionals

As the sector consolidates, people working on it gain experience and are more trained to perform their jobs. They also gain insight into training and accompanying junior staff. Therefore, the sector is growing and becoming more mature, translating into more trained professionals (although still insufficient) who can cover specific needs and new initiatives appearing that can cover different necessities. As one interviewee mentioned:

“Everyone has specialized. [It has helped] the journey of professionals and organizations that, almost all of them, ten years ago were starting. And we have been doing this for 8-9 years.” (Interviewee 1)

3.4.1.3 Increasing access to funding

As organizations grow, consolidate, and collaborate among them, they gain the capacity to access more complicated and professionalized funding sources, such as projects at a Spanish and European level. These projects allow organizations to share their expertise and knowledge and are usually an essential economic relief for social organizations that run, usually into tight budgets. As one interviewee stated:

“Having a law on the subject is very important. It helps you to have specific calls for subsidies that recognize you as an actor within a specific arena rather than pecking from different arenas.” (Interviewee 1)

3.4.1.4 Civil-society organization

The capacity of organic self-organization of the society of Barcelona has been seen as clear enabler for FWR. When collaboration with the administration is not feasible, the FSIs have grown thanks to public support, enabling themselves to cover the neighbours' needs through non-formal practices and even from squatted premises. An additional enabler of these non-formal is the inclusion of the diversity of the citizenship of Barcelona, caring for but also taking benefit of the different sensitivities. As an interviewee stated:

“[The initiative] works organically. And this is because is part of a social network, which was strong, and is strong in this neighbourhood. Also in communities, there is the social bond, the community bond.” (Interviewee 4)

3.4.1.5 Cooperation between administration and FSIs

From the point of view of both the administration and the FSIs, the will to work together exists, and common spaces of discussion, communication, and coordination have been created. From the administration's side, there is the consensus that the projects they lead are magnified when performed in tight collaboration with the existing FSIs. The tight collaboration between the administration and FSIs also relates to legislation, allowing for a fluent channel to seek clarification when necessary and consulting FSIs before legislating, including its expertise and the impact they foresee to have a wider understanding and adapting it to reality. Finally, this collaboration between FSIs and administration has also widened FSIs' options to access public funding by paving the way for developing specific sectorial subsidies for FWR activities, which even with the associated bureaucracy, has a very positive impact on FSIs' financial state. As two interviewees stated:

“While it might not have been the initial aim, these workspaces that were created by the law have ended up coordinating the sector a little bit.” (Interviewee 1)

“Barcelona is a pioneer city in the construction of collaboration strategies, public-social cooperation strategies. Many organisations cohesively roll up their sleeves and work for the welfare of the citizen.” (Interview 5)

3.4.1.6 Political will and committed public servants

The political will of the administration to work for FWR is signalled as one of the crucial issues by FSIs. Though the relation between administration and FSIs is heterogeneous, there is a shared perception that synergies have been facilitated by a progressive structure of the Catalan Government. This is particularly important because it gives specific stability to policies and programmes around food redistribution in the city and beyond. Also the Barcelona City Council has also fostered investment in innovative food infrastructure in the city, such as the FoodBack project, through major budget allocations.

“I think that there has been a commitment to support [FWR groups] via different ways, direct aid, subsidies and by defining roadmaps. I think they partially listen to us. I mean, a collaborative space has been created in the sense that the law pretty much reflected what all the sectors thought here.” (Interview 1)

3.4.1.7 Food waste recovery legislation

The administration also plays an essential role in legislation. Most FSIs identify the development of specific legislation for their operations as a key issue to be able to act; for example, gleaning was first codified in the Catalan Law for Food Waste Prevention (2020). Clear rules are necessary to know the actual constraints of their activities. Additionally to the laws, sometimes it is necessary to develop more practical guidelines that can help FSIs and businesses to adopt the proper measures, such as the guidelines developed by the agriculture departments regarding specific actions that actors of the food chain can adopt or the documents by the Catalan Food Safety Agency (together with Barcelona's competent body) to promote safe redistribution of food surplus. As an interviewee mentioned:

“It has helped a lot in the sense that before we did things because we thought they made sense and because we argued that they made sense. And now we can always say that we are enforcing a law, that we are obliged to do this. So, of course, this helps a lot. And that the law obliges the Catalan Government to have a strategic plan for Catalonia and to quantify. It helps us because the law moves bigger wheels than your own push.” (Interviewee 1)

3.4.1.8 Right to food

Organizations working in FWR consider that the rest of the enablers and their daily activities are built upon previous efforts to raise awareness of public opinion about food poverty and food waste prevention. Lately, public opinion has started to recognize the importance of fresh food and the empowerment of users, fostering the replacement of a charitable structure of FWR systems. Also, having such a rich environment for FSIs would not have been possible without the work done to make the problem known among the city's citizens. This remains true for collaboration with the administration. Long-term work must continue to be done to ensure that public opinion remains favourable, therefore fostering new initiatives and putting pressure on the administration to collaborate and subsidize FWR initiatives.

“Barcelona has a social fabric of organisations specialized in the field of food that are the engine of many of the solutions offered to many citizens who are in a situation of vulnerability. [...] Barcelona is taking on a responsibility in the area of food.” (Interviewee 3)

3.4.2 Main barriers of food waste redistribution

3.4.2.1 Lack of funding

Food Sharing Initiatives have to deal with a permanent precarity caused by the difficulties in funding. FSIs complain that the principal cause is their dependency on public subsidies, as their activities are usually not monetized in the regular market, forcing them to apply periodically and therefore not allowing for advanced planning. This leads to financial instability, as subsidies are awarded mostly after the completion of the project or action. Some FSIs also depend on private donations, which are still irregular funding sources.

One of the obstacles is the instability of funding [...] These are projects driven by entrepreneurship, they need a lot of personal drive. We have to dedicate a lot of professional

efforts. Projects work because there are people inside the organisations who believe in them. But there is a certain precariousness in all organizations. *[For example]*, one organization had to close its project for a few months because it had not received funding. Payments are late. (Interview 1)

3.4.2.2 Lack of trained professionals

Due, in part, to the precarity mentioned above, FSIs have to deal with a lack of staff trained in the field of FLW that are difficult to uptake and retain in the organizations, which still depend highly on voluntary work. The sector has grown rapidly (mostly out of pure necessity), and the number of capable professionals has not matched this growth to take on these tasks. This lack of trained professionals is highly relevant for FSIs that have to perform complicated logistic operations, as little mistakes can lead to the loss of tons of food. Additionally, the increase of fresh food in food distributed through FSIs has increased the complexity of food handling due to its perishability, rendering this lack of professionals more blatant. As an interviewee explained:

“Other obstacles are the growth of the sector itself, of the social organisations, and professionalization means that *[as an organisation]* you reach a point where there are not many more trained professionals than those who work already and have expertise in the organisations. And that there is a learning curve for the new ones that you have to train.” (Interviewee 1)

3.4.2.3 Perception of right to food

While there is a growing concern regarding food security, there is still a big barrier caused by the social stigma around food redistribution, which, even though FSIs acknowledge a positive shift, is still seen from a charity perspective, making it more challenging to undertake empowering projects. From the administration's perspective, though some projects like Alimenta are trying to shift from the traditional approach, they find it difficult to break the “social food” view and encourage models that take dignity and empowerment to the users. As an interviewee mentioned:

“Together with the social organizations, we have three physical spaces spread across the city of Barcelona. There, our goal is that people who turn to us to cover their food needs, do so in non-stigmatizing ways. We want to move away from what, for example, could be hunger queues. We want these spaces not only be focused on food, but also spaces that can guarantee people's work and social integration, grant access to the kitchen, facilitate community cooking activities, organise zero waste food workshops, etc.” (Interview 5)

3.4.2.4 Decrease in accessibility to food

FSIs show a relevant dependence on food availability, which is primarily an external factor. As food prices increase, it becomes more difficult to find steady sources of food to recover, as companies make bigger efforts to reduce food waste, and more people face food insecurity. While some organizations were making considerable efforts to cover the increasing demand for healthy and adequate food (with the increases in logistical difficulties and economic impact that this supposes)

and to develop empowering programs and activities, the added pressure caused by the price of food and scarcity of food recovery options (which worsens in a vicious cycle, as higher prices reduce food waste) made some of them focus into food security. These cultural and environmental issues are sometimes not being prioritized as organizations constantly face an even more pressing obstacle: the mismatch between the demand for donated food and the available food to redistribute. As an interviewee stated:

“We are not able to cover the food for all the people who go to a social services center, for example, and they have to be linked to a food resource.” (Interviewee 5)

3.4.2.5 Lack of infrastructure

One of the factors that is caused by FSIs’ chronic lack of funding is the lack of infrastructure to develop its activities. FSIs usually depend on ceded spaces by the administration or private entities, and only the most significant organizations can also rely on their economic capacity. Finally, non-formal, grounded organizations sometimes have to turn to (or do so due to political motivations) other practices such as squatted premises. As an interviewee explained:

“[It’s important to have] adequate spaces. [...] We were lucky that this big space was available, in some way, at a time with many restrictions like the curfew and distance and all that. [...] 90 people came looking for food. [...] It is also necessary, in general, to have a space to store food or to store it in decent conditions without stink or having animals that want to eat it. It’s pretty necessary to have fridges or something, it should be basic, but we do what we can.” (Interviewee 4)

3.4.2.6 Language barriers

The administration faces several difficulties when communicating with the different agents. Language barriers, in the case of grocery stores or other private initiatives run by migrants, can be an important one. They are not only a difficulty for oral communication but can also be a barrier to correctly implementing legislation and asking for subsidies or other kinds of help from the administration. As an interviewee said:

“There were communication difficulties. Many of these franchisees were people of foreign nationalities and therefore, it was very difficult for them to understand the message and to understand the project.” (Interviewee 2)

3.4.2.7 Bureaucracy

This is a major barrier for FSIs. As they depend on resources (mostly funding) from the administration, they must play by the rules when asking for subsidies, dealing with rigid and slow bureaucracy that makes them spend much time justifying projects rather than doing “actual” things. As an interviewee explained:

“We are doing a part of public services, social services, contributing to a social problem. But applying for subsidies means that we have to depend on the times, the dynamics and the

subsidy schedule. And we have to be applying constantly, applying for *[grants]* and probably not making as much of an impact *[as we could]*. Because we depend on subsidies. To give the example of Barcelona, the calls are made public in January to be presented in February. They are resolved in July, and the project needs to be finished in December. And we start again. *[In these tasks represent]* sometimes fifty percent of the money you have to justify.” (Interview 1)

3.4.2.8 Food waste recovery legislation

The legislation on food waste, food safety, and their interaction is sometimes unclear. Though the administration has tried to clarify it through specific guidelines, it is sometimes too limiting and hinders food recovery. As an interviewee stated:

“The most clear is that as we work with products that have a very short shelf life, we have to be very agile because we manage many millions of kilos.” (Interviewee 5)

3.4.2.9 Perception from the private sector

Systemic difficulties due to different cultural values and frames arise when dealing with private companies, especially with franchises or multi-store businesses, as they usually feel blamed when considering food waste issues and are unwilling to collaborate, or the administration has problems identifying the right spokesperson. As an interviewee explained:

“Many establishments are franchises. Many of these franchises told us that they depended on the head office. That they did not have the freedom to participate in a project like this, but then when they contacted the head office, many organisations said that they did not have the capacity to influence the establishments, or that they were not interested in participating in the project.” (Interviewee 2)

3.4.2.10 Cooperation between FSIs

FSIs are usually not vertically integrated, forcing them to cooperate. This interaction causes friction due to the sizes, objectives, and professionalization level. One problem is the difficulty of aligning the rhythms between FSIs where food is recovered. More significant, more professionalized FSIs (even though they face some of the difficulties pointed out before) sometimes have difficulties finding recipient organizations that can guarantee a high and regular reception rate of food, as they are sometimes formed mainly by volunteers. As an interviewee said:

“We work with many organisations and these organisations, at the same time, reach people in vulnerable situations through different ways, either in social canteens, or in residences, or in sheltered housing, or in solidarity food distribution, or in social commissary to different profiles and groups.” (Interviewee 5)

3.4.2.11 Lack of volunteers

Another barrier is that social polarization creates divisions between individuals who are not involved in any organization and extremely politicized individuals who do not feel comfortable participating in systemic non-ideological food charities. This empties this middle space of individuals who are not politically involved but are willing to collaborate with FSIs in their free time. As an interviewee explained:

“An obstacle to the sector in general or to neighbourhood social organizations is that they depend on their volunteers, who are older people who are retired. *[Volunteers]* sometimes burn out, sometimes leave, sometimes rotate.” (Interviewee 1)

3.4.2.12 Internal organizational problems

Different internal dynamics make its functioning more difficult within organizations, especially the most non-formal ones. Some organisations comment the difficulty of having visible privileges (race, sex, origin) between members of organizations and to minimize its incidence. Also, the formation of a vanguard comprised of those more actively involved in decision-making spaces and the undervaluation of reproductive tasks that are crucial for the group's functioning, usually do less privileged individuals. As an interviewee explained:

“Activism and participation I think are often measured, in political terms, in terms of participation in the assembly. And the physical component is greatly underestimated, the more demanding component. To go to recover food, to clean it and such. I would consider this an attitude that tends to racism as well, in some way, because it's obviously a class issue, it's an issue of origin as well. Who worked and did not participate politically? Well, it was people, especially of migrant origin. There were many people who participated a lot, but somehow they became invisible.” (Interviewee 4)

3.5 Social, Political and Ecologic Context

In general, regional and Spanish dynamics seem to be more relevant than municipal initiatives in shaping the FWR practices in Barcelona.

Some of these regional dynamics that foster the work of FWR initiatives are the work of the Catalan Waste Agency on food waste prevention for many years, which has been followed up by the Agricultural Department of the Catalan Government. For many years, they have created different lines of subsidies and grants dedicated to reducing food waste in Catalonia. Also, participating in different European projects has successfully promoted cooperation and collaboration between different FWR entities. Even though these subsidies have a regional scope, most of the beneficiaries are in Barcelona city and its metropolitan area. A perfect example of the successful work of the FWR entities in Catalonia culminated with the creation of the Ley 3/2020 – LPPMA, Law for Food Waste Prevention, which was a bottom-up initiative. The climate and social context of crisis have also favoured all these governmental initiatives.

Barcelona's tradition of self-organization and solidarity, rooted in movements like anarcho-syndicalism, continues to support grassroots initiatives and FSIs. These initiatives thrive within a

mutual support network and benefit from strong social legitimacy. These grassroots efforts influence the public administration, and the city's political culture encourages high participation in such organizations, fostering their growth and sustainability.

Another relevant contextual pattern that affects the daily practices of FSIs is a series of interconnected urban dynamics, including gentrification, turistification, and displacement. These are reflected in the real estate market, with housing and shop prices (both rental and acquisition) breaking records year after year. The direct consequence is that FSIs are increasingly struggling to find suitable spaces for their activities, especially in certain neighbourhoods, such as Raval. In short, we could say that the wild dynamics of neoliberal urbanism are threatening the political tradition and culture of the city.

Another significant trend affecting FSIs is the increased presence of migrant communities in Barcelona. While international migration has been high for some time, its economic impact, such as the rise of migrant-run food businesses, is relatively recent. Both public administration and FSIs have had to adapt to this new reality, finding common values and communication methods. In districts like Ciutat Vella, migrant communities have formed solidarity networks that support their members and can either relieve FSIs of some responsibilities or cooperate with them. However, these migrant networks typically do not interact with local networks, limiting potential coordination, except in cases like the Xarxa d'Aliments d'El Raval.

Derived from the lockdown during the COVID-19 pandemic, many new support networks were created in all Barcelona neighbourhoods. They aimed to assist neighbours in highly vulnerable conditions due to their health status, financial constraints, or social isolation. Today, some of these networks are still active.

Finally, the political context of the Barcelona City Council in previous years was also relevant to the development and growth of the FWR system in Barcelona. It was framed within its social and environmental sustainability work in the city. The "Barcelona en comú" party governed the city for eight years. Thanks to their efforts and other entities in the city and its metropolitan and regional area, Barcelona became 2021 World Capital of Sustainable Food. This triggered many projects related to sustainable food and diets, including food waste prevention, such as FWR.

3.6 Policy Recommendations

3.6.1 For the Barcelona City Council

- Set and define guidelines for safely redistributing food surpluses (e.g., Guidelines for Safe Donations, Safe Donations from ACSA). From public administrations, general guidelines could be established outlining the most relevant criteria to consider throughout food redistribution. They could also serve as a reference entity to address queries and promote safe donations across the territory or refer to other organizations for such purposes.
- Inform and educate the public health inspectors of the Catalan Agency of Food Safety and the Barcelona Food Safety Agency on safe food redistribution so they can promote it during their work time. This issue is essential because while zero risk does not exist, except for the non-redistribution of food, efforts should be made to minimize the risk to the maximum

extent possible to fully acceptable levels. This is because the issue of food loss and waste is a problem that deserves to be addressed and reduced.

- Encourage agrifood companies, from producers to retailers and food services, to reduce food loss and waste at their source and donate it to social entities for food redistribution. Basically, this means applying the Lay 03/2020 of Food Loss and Waste Prevention. To achieve this, it will be necessary for public administrations to establish awareness-raising strategies tailored to economic sectors, demonstrating the reduction of food loss and waste as a pathway to business improvement and highlighting the economic, environmental, and social benefits associated with this reduction. Identifying pioneering companies that can serve as a driving force to influence a large portion of the sector and promoting good practices in this regard are also crucial points to foster a commitment to addressing this issue.
- Provide more stable and long-term funding to the FWR initiatives.
- Promote the training of professionals in food loss and waste to work in the FSI so that they can depend to a lesser extent on voluntary work for crucial tasks like logistics.
- Facilitate second-hand facilities and machines for FWR initiatives, such as refrigerators, to extend the shelf life of donated perishable products and prevent food waste in their facilities.
- Promote more qualified equipment such as blast chillers, accompanied by guidelines on efficiently using these devices in safe food redistribution.

3.6.2 FSIs

- Establish broader distribution networks and communication among them, enabling coordination to set priorities for receiving and collecting food by entities, coordinating distributions based on inventory, and facilitating the entire network's assimilation of most surplus food.
- Increase collaborations with scientific and technical entities to address existing technical and logistical challenges.

3.6.3 Private Sector

- Comply with the Lay 03/2020 requirements of Food Loss and Waste prevention and consequently: (1) develop and implement a Food Loss and Waste Reduction and Prevention Plan; (2) collaborate with local FSI to prevent FLW through food redistribution. To achieve this, the involvement of the Management is crucial to permeate the need to address the issue of food loss and waste throughout the company, allowing the establishment of foundations for generating bottom-up improvements and innovations, fostering synergies between both dynamics.
- Rise awareness and educate their employees on the food loss and waste problem and the right to food.
- Communicate the actions they have applied to their food waste reduction, along with their reduction or prevention impact, in terms of positive impact at the economic, environmental, and social levels, to inspire other companies in the private sector.

4. Governance landscape of food-related Social and Solidarity Economy initiatives

4.1 Introduction

Global crises, such as the 2008 economic crisis or the COVID-19 crisis, combined with growing calls for sustainability and equity, have brought attention to a group of economic actors that are neither public nor for-profit. These actors implement alternative business models and are known as the social and solidarity economy (SSE). The SSE is just one of several terms used to describe these models, including the third sector, the social economy, the solidarity economy, and the non-profit sector. As the OECD states:

The concept of the SSE developed from the merging of two notions: the social economy and the solidarity economy. Historically consisting of associations, cooperatives and mutual societies, the social economy has recently extended to include foundations and social enterprises, while the solidarity economy also includes more spontaneous community-based initiatives emerging at the grassroots level. The resulting plurality of organisations, purposes, practices, business models and legal entities that have emerged across OECD member states and beyond makes it challenging to develop a common definition of the SSE and a clear delineation of its scope. Among the diverse notions, the SSE is the most encompassing term and is increasingly used by practitioners and academics, as well as at the international level. (OECD, 2023)

SSE organisations allocate ownership rights and organise decision-making processes differently, enabling the mobilisation of a diverse set of market and non-market resources. Collaboration and cooperation are core values of SSE organisations, enabling them to develop partnerships with other SSE entities as well as public and private actors to achieve social objectives and access resources.

The social economy employs more than 10% of the active population and contributes 8% of Catalonia's GDP (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2021a). Barcelona is a city worldwide known for its support of SSE. While the history of SSE is rooted and shaped by the strong Catalan workers cooperative movement in the 19th and 20th centuries, the left-wing electoral coalition Barcelona en Comú, which won the municipal elections in 2015, institutionally adopted and helped develop the sector of SSE in the city to play a more prominent role. Food is one of the areas developed by the SSE sector in Barcelona. Currently, there are more than 140 food-related projects in Barcelona (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2024) acting in many areas of the food system: production, distribution, commercialisation, catering, and dynamisation.

The primary goal of this report is to enhance comprehension of the governance landscape surrounding food-related SSE initiatives in Barcelona. This implies, on the one hand, understanding the regulatory framework that affects and conditions the practice of these activities, as well as knowing the map of actors involved, and understanding the type of relations formed between the actors involved in these initiatives. Also, understanding the food-related social and solidarity economy governance landscape involves appreciating and describing the diversity of projects that

exist in the city. Furthermore, it is also crucial to recognise the main obstacles hindering the benefits of these initiatives and the enablers that promote their success. The ultimate purpose of this report is to provide recommendations for the local government, shared food initiatives, and the private sector to support food-related social and solidarity economy expansion and improvement.

4.2 Regulatory regimes shaping social and solidarity economy

There are different laws and regulatory frameworks that affect food-related SEE initiatives. The most relevant ones for each level of governance are:

4.2.1 European regulatory framework

Under European legislation, SEE is recognised as Social Economy. The European Commission promotes the development of social economy enterprises and organisations mainly via the Single Market Programme. Additionally, it is also particularly focused on supporting the development of the social economy by implementing the European action plan on social economy (2021).

4.2.2 Spanish Regulatory Framework

The Spanish state has also its own laws regulating cooperatives (BOE, 1999) and the social economy (BOE, 2011a). Apparently, these laws will be combined into a new integral law of the social economy. A preliminary bill for this new law was drafted in 2023 and approved by the government, and it is currently pending parliamentary approval. Until this law was approved, SSE stakeholders based in Catalonia were regulated by the Catalan legislation, which was more specific and encompassing than the Spanish. The Spanish laws were thus addressed to cover SSE stakeholders in those autonomous regions where there were no updated laws on the matter.

In April 2023, the Spanish government approved the Spanish Strategy of Social Economy 2023-2027 (BOE, 2023). The SSE is regarded in this document as a key element to contribute to the recovery of the Spanish economy, particularly, in a context of social and economic uncertainties. The strategy contains a SWOT analysis describing some of the weaknesses, strengths, threats and opportunities of the sector. The following table summarises the content of this SWOT analysis.

Table 1. SWOT analysis from the Spanish Strategy of Social Economy 2023-2027. Source: Own elaboration, BOE (2023)

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Resilient companies, which prioritise sustainability over short-term results ● Solid associative framework and plurality of actors and organisational structures ● Alignment of the SSE with the 2030 Agenda ● Leadership of the Spanish SSE in Europe ● Greater institutional presence of the SSE in the political and regulatory sphere, both in Spain and in Europe ● Business model rooted in the territories ● Contribution to social cohesion through the creation of quality and inclusive employment ● Specialisation of the SE in strategic sectors (health, care, agri-food, energy and circular economy) ● Great capacity to generate social innovation schemes, relationships and actions with participatory approaches ● A key player in public-private cooperation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scarce visibility of SSE ● Lack of statistical data to understand the situation, evolution and impacts. ● Lack of participation in cross-cutting legislative processes. ● Lack of capacity to escalate successful innovation processes ● Weaknesses in collaborative structures ● Lack of participation in funding and support not specific to the sector. ● Scarce digitalisation ● Difficulties in gaining long-term funding support ● Gender gap, especially in roles of responsibility ● Difficulties to gain relative weight in the economy ● Scarce education on SSE in universities ● Insufficient presence of the sector in the technological sector.
THREATS	OPPORTUNITIES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Confusion of the concept of "Social Economy" with new terms - "social companies", or "companies with impact" - which relate to business models that do not follow the principles of the SE. ● Lack of knowledge of the SE (concept, regulations, economic reality, socioeconomic impact) in public administrations, with the exception of specific departments. ● Little integration and interdepartmental and inter-institutional coordination. ● Underfunding of resources (human and budgetary) of specific departments ● Limited level of entrepreneurship in society, especially among the young population 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Growing demand for educational and social services that can be covered by the SSE. ● Society demands greater involvement from companies in addressing economic, social and environmental challenges. ● Implementation of new business paradigms ● Possible development of the open clause of Law 5/2011 of ESS (article 5.2.) to incorporate new business realities ● New participatory financing options ● Progress in the equality of SSE members and workers in labour rights ● Inclusion of social clauses in public procurement regulations ● Greater focus of public policies on the development of sectors where SE has an important specialisation ● Growing trend towards public-private cooperation in sectors where SE has competitive advantages

From this SWOT analysis, the Spanish Strategy of Social Economy 2023-2027 describes four strategic axes and 18 strategic action lines emerged. These are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of the strategic axes and action lines of the Spanish Strategy of Social Economy 2023-2027

AXE 1	AXE 2	AXE 3	AXE 4
Visibility and institutional participation in the social economy	Improving competitiveness	Entrepreneurship and emerging sectors	Social and territorial sustainability
Strengthen the visibility of SSE at the institutional level and in the regulatory framework	Raise the levels of internationalisation of the SSE	Increase the presence of the SSE in new entrepreneurship initiatives	Advance gender equality in the SSE
Promote the recognition of SSE among social agents and society as a whole	Increase innovation and digital transformation of the SSE	Improve the integration of SSE in the innovative “ecosystem” and in technology-based entrepreneurship	Promote equal opportunities in groups with difficulties in accessing employment
Consolidate the presence of the SSE in the Agenda of international institutions	Promote the updating of skills and professional requalification in SSE	Strengthen the competitive position of the SSE in emerging sectors	Promote generational change in the SSE
Promote the production and dissemination of statistics related to SSE	Increase intra- and inter-sector cooperation of SSE companies and entities.		Promote the contribution of the SSE to territorial cohesion and depopulation
Promote analysis to measure the economic and social impact of the SSE	Increase the green transformation of SSE companies and entities		

Source: Own elaboration from BOE (2023)

In addition to laws regulating cooperatives and the social economy as a whole, regulations affect specifically food-related SEE initiatives at the Spanish level.

For example, the legislation on food safety (BOE, 2011b) or on public health, which is regulated regionally (DOGC, 2009). This is articulated in the requirement of a certificate for food handlers, which is granted to individuals after they undergo specific training.

Another relevant food regulation at the Spanish level is the Food Chain Law (BOE, 2021). This law seeks to establish fair economic relations among the different actors of the food chain from production to distribution. However, the enforcement of this law seems to be questionable. As an interviewee pointed out:

[*The Food Chain Law*] lacks an enforcing body. Nobody checks if the law is actually being followed. (Interview 1)

4.2.3 Catalan regulatory framework

In the Catalan context, Law 12/2015 on Catalan Cooperatives gives official recognition to cooperatives of all kinds and establishes their right to carry out economic and social activity (DOGC,

2021a). This law attempts to reflect in a legal framework the seven cooperative principles issued by the International Cooperative Alliance, the independent association that unites represents and serves cooperatives worldwide. In recent years, though, the Catalan government and several organisations representative of the SSE have been working together on creating a new law that is representative of all SSE stakeholders. The future SSE law will seek to recognise the SSE as a key pillar of the Catalan plural economy, with the goal of advancing towards economic democracy. It will establish a specific legal framework for the SSE, pursuing a higher institutional presence to foster the development of the SSE in Catalonia. A preliminary document was completed by the end of 2020, and in 2021 the Generalitat opened a participatory process in which all stakeholders of the SSE were able to give feedback. An official report on the impact of this law summarised the following three main barriers for the SSE sector (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2023:6):

- There is a lack of knowledge and visibility of the social and solidarity economy in a large part of society in general and in public administrations, despite the growing demand from citizens that their work, their consumption, their savings, and their investments have a more ethical and social impact and meaning.
- The difficulty in accessing suitable financing to cover their needs regards their distinctive features not as a handicap or impediment to access to financing but as a positive element to be valued.
- The initial unbalanced conditions of SSE initiatives difficulting competition with companies or operators with purely commercial objectives.

Currently, a bill draft that will include the feedback received is being written, but the 2024 Catalan elections have thrown further uncertainty over when this bill will be finally approved.

The potential overlapping between the Spanish and Catalan laws is perceived by some members of cooperatives as a possible challenge. As an interviewee pointed out:

There is a new SSE law being developed in Catalonia. But it turns out that the Spanish government is promoting a national SSE law as well, which has been told that it will be the main SSE law. And this is a terrible game because we're constantly like: "Where should we look now"? (Interview 2)

4.2.4 Municipal programs addressing food-related SSE initiatives

4.2.4.1 Plans to develop the Social and Solidarity Economy sector

In 2015, the Barcelona local government created an inter-institutional body, the Social and Solidarity Economy Commission and developed the [Impetus Plan for Social and Solidarity Economy in Barcelona \(2016-2019\)](#), a socially innovative action program which aims to strengthen and formalise collaboration between the local government and civil society groups engaged in social economies. Between 2016 and 2018, the plan managed 11 million euros in ongoing expenses and received 1.9 million euros in investments. As Chaves-Avila and Gallego-Bono (2020:15) describe: "This plan was systematised in a complex architecture of objectives, instruments, responsible bodies, and monitoring and evaluation indicators. It contained two major general objectives, 6 lines of work, 24 specific objectives, and 31 specific actions. The major objectives were the promotion of new initiatives, the transformation of traditional companies into entities of the SSE and the

strengthening of existing SSE entities. [...] More specifically, the Plan contained various instruments for both hard and soft policies. These were: (1) financial support instruments, such as budgets and public, private and public-private financing mechanisms; (2) cognitive support instruments, such as awareness and dissemination instruments, reports and statistics, as well as training activities; (3) technical support and advisory instruments, and support for innovation; (4) instruments to support access to public markets, such as public procurement and the social market; (5) unique and referential instruments; and finally, (6) instruments to support the creation and development of social and participatory capital, such as networks of entities, and shared facilities. Many of the instruments applied, such as the social market or the projects for emblematic collective spaces, are political innovations, typical of a new transformative policy”.

The support to SSE continued after this Plan ended with the [Social and Solidarity Economy Boost Plan in Barcelona, 2021-2023](#). This new Plan follows and adapts the roadmap set out by the Barcelona 2030 Social and Solidarity Economy Strategy (see below) while identifying, prioritising and applying the actions with the most impact on municipal public policy. The new Plan, a working document that facilitates the implementation of the Strategy in the municipal sphere, has been adopted through the participatory process involving Barcelona City Council and the SSE sector in the city. It has 12 objectives and 65 actions; it was developed by the Social Economy team of Barcelona City Council and Barcelona Activa's Socioeconomic Innovation and has an overall budget of 12 million euros in current expenditure, 7.8 million in investments and 2 million in possible investment fund (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2021).

When writing this report, after this second plan ended, the Barcelona City Council was in the process of approving the Social and Solidarity Plan in Barcelona 2024-2027.

4.2.4.2 Barcelona 2030 Social and Solidarity Economy Strategy

Between 2019 and 2021, several SSE stakeholders and the Barcelona City Council worked collectively on creating the [Barcelona 2030 Strategy for Social and Solidarity Economy](#) (ESSBCN2030). The participatory process included 147 SSE stakeholders and was heavily influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic, which affected a shift of priorities along the way. The strategy was organised around eight strategic lines that seek to increase the productive significance of the SSE in the city, foster collaborations and develop collective infrastructures among SSE stakeholders, and promote public policies that further support the SSE. These lines of work have indicators and milestones and are articulated into ten city projects that propose concrete actions to boost the strategic lines. Some of these projects, for instance, plan to develop sectorial SSE strategies to promote training and education for SSE or consolidate Coòpolis (the Ateneu Cooperatiu de Barcelona). Food is considered one of the ten strategic sectors of the ESSBCN2030, particularly valued because of its importance in fulfilling basic needs, its connection with existing SSE projects and social movements in the city, and its potential to effect social and environmental change. The governance of the strategy is structured in two different levels. The first level is formed by the so-called promoting organisations, a mix of SSE federations and networks, public actors and sectorial associations. This level forms the executive core group and has a majority presence in the wider participatory assembly and the workgroups. The second level is open to all SSE stakeholders willing to adhere to the strategy, with 219 signatories currently. These have a certain presence in the participatory assembly and can also join work groups.

Programs and mechanisms to shape the food-related Social and Solidarity Sector

The Barcelona City Council is a relevant economic agent and shapes the city's political economy. In 2017, the Council reviewed the environmental and social criteria for public procurement and included social and ecological aspects to promote responsible public procurement in all municipal tenders. This is one of the primary mechanisms to promote ESS and food-related ESS.

[Social clauses in public procurement:](#) With the Decree of April 24, 2017, Barcelona City Council promoted socially responsible public procurement that incorporates social justice objectives and promotes the social and labour rights of those hired. The Social Clauses, as well as the Social Reserve, are mechanisms of the City Council to reinforce social policies, create job placement opportunities for people with special difficulties and strengthen and promote the SSE in the city (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2017).

There are also many municipal programs that aim to support SSE initiatives, including food-related SSE initiatives. Most of the main municipal programs supporting food-related SEE initiatives are located within the umbrella of the support Barcelona Activa, the municipal institution that develops economic policies and local development and grants to SSE initiatives. These are divided into the following categories:

General programs:

- [Training & education to SSE organisations:](#) These are short trainings created to provide tools to SSE organisations in one of the following areas: 1) communication tools and strategies; 2) Finance management; 3) Strategic planning; 4) Support with an understanding of public tenders. These trainings are carried out in single-session format (a single session) and multi-session (in more than one day or session) and combine face-to-face sessions with virtual ones.
- [Consulting services:](#) The Social and Solidarity Economy Consulting Service is a specific and personalised public service for SSE initiatives. The service offers advice on creating ideas, legislation, taxation, communication, financing, team organization and management, and business plan support.
- [InnoBa:](#) A public facility run by Barcelona Activa that offers activities, specialized services, research, training and spaces for experimentation and incubation in the fields of the Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE) and Socioeconomic Innovation. It is aimed at both those people and organisations that want to have first contact with the Social and Solidarity Economy and those that already have projects underway.
- [InnoBAdora+:](#) The Incubation Community for Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE) organisations that seek to consolidate and develop in a collaborative environment and with holistic and comprehensive support, both at an expert level and among peers. The community has an incubation aspect, located in a physical space, InnoBA, the Center for Socioeconomic Innovation of Barcelona, but it goes beyond this physical space with different levels of membership and services.
- [DiesInnoBA:](#) A program of activities in an innovative format that aims to bring SSE and socioeconomic innovation closer to the general public, disseminating inspiring practices and

experiences and promoting dialogue between SSE initiatives and commercial companies, promoting hybridisation.

Targeted Programs

- [“Let’s reimagine”](#): A program to help transform and promote the resilience of companies and entities with practices and values of the Social and Solidarity Economy or that are in the process of incorporating them and want to have a positive environmental, social, and good governance impact.
- [Program for the organisation of care](#): Advice for organisations that provide care services from the Social and Solidarity Economy, especially those dedicated to caring for dependent people, home care and personal assistance.
- [“Women, let’s build” \(Construïm en femení, originally\)](#): It is a training and support program for entrepreneurship projects in the Social and Solidarity Economy aimed at women. It wants to make visible cooperative, social and solidarity entrepreneurship initiatives promoted by women and support them by offering a training program with a gender vision that contributes to creating a reference space for cooperative, social and solidarity entrepreneurs.
- [Path to Strength](#): Program to support and strengthen Social and Solidarity Economy organisations managed and led by women or that want to focus on training workers in positions of responsibility.
- [#transformESS Program](#): It promotes SSE and cooperativism among young people, both in the different educational stages of formal education (primary education, secondary education, training cycles and high school) and other non-formal educational spaces.
- [“Shutters up”](#): In 2023, The Barcelona City Council activated two calls, one specifically for social and solidarity economy, to attract projects for 36 municipal premises on the ground floor. These municipal premises were offered cheaper than the market price (i.e., successful applicants could rent them for between 30% and 50% of the market price).

4.3 Subsidies and Grants

In the last years, SSE has received an important amount of public support in Catalonia, especially in Barcelona. The most relevant materialisation of this trend has been a prominent stream of public funding that has reached SSE projects through different lines of subsidies at both regional and local levels. Whereas this support is not exclusively directed to food-related SSE projects, food-sharing initiatives (FSIs) that fall within the SSE realm benefit from public funding.

4.3.1 Spanish and European Subsidies

In the context of the Next Generation EU funds, the Spanish state is offering a specific yearly subsidy to support the development of the social economy at the national scale. Awarded projects must be active in at least two Spanish autonomous regions. The budget allocation for the 2022-2023 period

was 10,2 million euros directed to support initiatives that create jobs, strengthen the European productive sector from a social economy standpoint, and promote digitalisation.

4.3.2 Subsidies from the Catalan government

The Catalan government has three primary programs to grant financial help to SSE organisations: *Ateneus cooperatius*, *Singulars* projects, and Urban Communalities.

The most impactful line of subsidies offered by the Catalan Government has been securing a budget to run the network of [Ateneus Cooperatius](#). This is a territorial network of 14 cooperative hubs covering all of the Catalan territory, which are devoted to promoting and supporting the development of the SSE (see more information in the next section). Created in 2016, the Network of Cooperative Ateneus (*Xarxa d'Ateneus Cooperatius*) has been allocated over 16 million euros for the 2021-2024 (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2021b). SSE stakeholders¹ and municipalities (usually forming consortiums) receive and manage the funds and have to present multi-year projects.

Another crucial element of the Catalan financial support to the SSE is the [Singulars projects](#), which have been allocated 3,5 million euros for the 2021-2024. This subsidy aims to fund strategic projects within the SSE, emphasising increasing employment opportunities. To do so, the Catalan government supports the creation of new cooperatives or intercooperation projects (second-degree cooperatives) through yearly calls, which can cover up to 70.000 euros for each application. The Singulars grants are usually considered the main source of public funding by SSE actors.

Additionally, the Catalan government has recently secured a new funding stream to support the development of [Urban Commonalities](#) (*Comunalitats Urbanes*, in Catalan). This programme has established a territorial network of 22 Commonalities, which seek to expand the scope of the SSE by including local and community economies. In Barcelona, there are five commonalities in the city districts of Poble-sec, Sants, Nou Barris, Sant Andreu and Ciutat Vella (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2024). The program also has an office that coordinates, accompanies, and equips the Network of the 22 Commonalities to face the challenges of the program together. It also provides technical and administrative support, ensuring good traceability and functioning of the Commonalities' actions. Created in 2022, the network of Urban Commonalities has been allocated a budget of 9,85 million euros for the 2024-2026 period. These grants provide each urban Commonality with up to €350,000 for developing its lines of action throughout the two years of the programme (DOGC, 2021b). Interestingly, the Urban Commonalities programme has defined food sovereignty as one of its key strategic lines.

Additionally, other funding lines cover a diversity of purposes, such as training, dissemination, promotion, and coordination of the SSE. These have been allocated over 1,6 million euros for the 2021-2024 period and are mostly directed to reinforcing the cultural presence of the SSE values in Catalonia (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2021b)

¹ These are mostly workers' cooperatives, but other types of cooperatives, associations, foundations and mutualities are also legally considered as SSE stakeholders.

4.3.3 Subsidies from the Barcelona City Council

There are two main subsidy programs for SSE offered by the Barcelona City Council: “Enfortim l’Economia Social Solidària” (literally meaning “We strengthen the SSE” in Catalan) and “Impulsem el Què Fas” (meaning We boost what you do in Catalan).

[“Enfortim l’Economia Social Solidària”](#) was allocated 1,1 million euros in 2023 and has been offered yearly for the past seven years. It funds up to 80% of the expenses to projects contributing to the SSE city strategy 2030 and the municipal plans for boosting the SSE. More specifically, it aims to support the creation of new SSE initiatives, strengthen the presence of the SSE, and foster intercooperation in Barcelona. The Enfortim subsidy is organised into six categories, of which four are particularly relevant for SSE FSIs:

Sustainable food and responsible consumption: this category is directed to economic and social projects that contribute to improving the food system in the city in line with the main premises defined by the Healthy and Sustainable Food City Strategy 2030 and the SSE City Strategy 2030 (see next section). It funds explicitly three types of projects: commercialisation and distribution of healthy, just and sustainable food; outreach and promotion of responsible consumption and sustainable food; and responsible consumption in education centres.

Socioeconomic innovation and SSE: This category includes innovative SSE projects that contribute to developing the strategic lines and objectives defined in the SSE City Strategy 2030 (see next section). Projects need to be aligned with the neighbourhood's needs and generate new economic activity.

“Shutters up”: This category is mostly directed at supporting the establishment of local businesses in previously empty ground-floor shops. It is a way to help small projects that would otherwise struggle with the Barcelona real estate market while bringing new life to the neighbourhoods.

“Last mile” urban distribution: this category seeks to fund projects that will improve efficiency and reduce the impact of urban delivery of food and other goods. Projects awarded must carry out last-mile delivery with zero-emissions vehicles.

[Impulsem el Què Fas](#) is a yearly subsidy allocated a budget of 2.5 million euros in 2023. The Impulsem subsidy is not exclusively directed to SSE stakeholders; it is also open to individuals and small enterprises. It funds 80% of the expenses (up to 40k euros) for projects grounded in their neighbourhood and contributes to boosting the local economies in Barcelona.

Additionally, in 2018, the Barcelona City Council developed an innovative public-private strategy to crowdfund ESS projects. This type of crowdfunding, called Jointly ([Conjuntament](#) in Catalan), constituted a new way of financing entrepreneurial initiatives, thanks to the 'matchfunding' formula that allows private and public money to be raised in collaboration between the different entities and the public. The result is a new crowdfunding method aimed at doubling the total investment for social and neighbourhood projects in Barcelona. With this method, the public administration has contributed one euro for each private euro contributed by a participating person. The campaign raised 231,336 euros (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2018).

4.4 Key food-related SSE projects

Barcelona has more than 140 food-related projects (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2024). In many of them, food-related SSE stakeholders, the public administration, and occasionally, the private sector collaborate. Below is a non-comprehensive list of some of them to illustrate the rich diversity of initiatives:

- **[Fair on responsible consumption and SSE](#)**: Organised by the Barcelona City Council, this week-long fair takes place every Christmas to promote and facilitate responsible consumption and the Social and Solidarity Economy (ESS) and offer quality, local products made under conditions that respect people and places. In addition, the fair contributes to giving visibility to and strengthening SSE companies and organisations and their activities.
- **[Terra Pagesa](#)**: a logistic and commercial hub located in Mercabarna (a hub of wholesale food markets) that facilitates the distribution of proximity products to small businesses and local markets. It introduces logistic and transport features that allow producers to reduce the time dedicated to commercial activities, which is a long-time demand by small farmers.
- **[Ecocentral](#)**: Ecocentral is an agroecological food purchasing centre that supplies school canteens. It works with over one hundred schools throughout Catalonia, serving organic food purchased directly from the producer. In addition to operating as a purchasing centre, Ecocentral advises its clients to transition from a traditional school canteen to an organic one. It has warehouses to place large orders at low prices and make deliveries according to weekly needs. It has a cooking workshop, fourth-range room and bulk repackaging; ultimately, it offers a comprehensive service tailored to each client.
- **[Opcions](#)**: Opcions is a non-profit cooperative that publishes information on how to consume less and better and offers advantages to make responsible consumption easier.
- **[Cooperativa Queviures](#)**: Wholesale distribution cooperative of organic and local products.
- **[Can Calopa/L'Olivera](#)**: Can Calopa de Dalt is the century-old farmhouse where the L'Olivera cooperative produces organic wines and olive oil. The cooperative incorporates vulnerable people with difficulties throughout the production process and creates opportunities for social inclusion for young people with special needs.
- **[Natursí](#)**: It is a second-degree cooperative created by a group of more than 20 independent organic stores to strengthen and expand the independent organic sector in Catalonia.
- **[Menjador Ca la Rosa](#)**: A non-profit working cooperative that promotes sustainable food and social market products as tools for the transformation of current food systems. Within the cooperative's project is the management of a restaurant bar at the Floristeria de Masadas and the Mercat de Pagès de La Sagrera.
- **[Foodcoop](#)**: the city's first cooperative supermarket, on the left side of the Eixample neighbourhood. Foodcoop BCN began in February 2022 and was supported by close to 500 members who decided to contribute capital and volunteer time to create their alternative to the big distributors.
- **[Kop de ma](#)**: Cooperative bar offering tortillas, craft beer, Basque wines and cider. They use local and solidarity economy products and try to dignify the work of the hospitality industry through the organisation as a work cooperative.

- [La Deskomunal](#): The Deskomunal is a cooperative project that aims to generate decent jobs, offer a quality cultural and gastronomic offering, and be a space in and for the Sants neighbourhood. It is a venue for live music and a restaurant that offers quality food with local products, a transformative economy, and popular prices.
- [La Coordinadora \(The Coordinator\)](#) is a second-level cooperative with common purposes, objectives, and criteria. It comprises the delegated persons from more than 40 consumption cooperatives in Barcelona, which have not lost their legal personality.

4.4.1 The diversity of food-related SSE initiatives

The food-related SSE sector in Barcelona is extremely diverse. This section maps out the main sub-sectors and actors of the food-related SSE in Barcelona. For that purpose, we use a broad conceptualisation of SSE that includes not only those FSIs that are legally constituted and/or have formal economic activity but also informal community economies that sometimes don't even recognise themselves as part of this system. We have divided the stakeholders into five categories that loosely match the food production chain: production, distribution, commercialisation, catering, and dynamisation.

4.4.1.1 Production

Three main types of actors populate this category: farming projects, community gardens and processing projects. The agroecological farming production within the city is anecdotal, with the only relevant project being Can Calopa, managed by *L'olivera* cooperative. As for community gardens, these are precisely at the boundaries of the SSE and are covered by the Urban Agriculture report. The last category is processing projects, known in Catalan as "obradors" (processing workshops). These produce various products: bread and pastries, preserves, beverages (alcoholic and non-alcoholic), etc. Moreover, at the time of writing, there is a collective food workshop (*obrador*, in Catalan), which is being developed in the premises of Can Batlló (a 13,000 m² self-managed community space in the Sants neighbourhood which is located in different buildings in the old textile factory of Can Batlló and which is ceded by the City Council) that aims to become a shared infrastructure for several existing and new SSE projects in the city.

4.4.1.2 Distribution

There are two types of SSE initiatives whose activities are focused on distribution in the city: wholesale (i.e., enterprises involved in moving products from their manufacturers or original suppliers to retailers) and last-mile distribution (i.e., the very last step of the delivery process when a parcel is moved from a transportation hub to its final destination). While crucial, wholesale distribution has historically been a weak link within the food-related SSE. Until recently, the only SSE general wholesale distributor in the city was Quèviure, a second-degree coop that gathers several small agroecological producers. Regarding specific sectors, Ecocentral is a project that connects small agroecological producers with school canteens. On the other hand, last-mile distribution is a well-developed sector in Barcelona. Three cyclologistics cooperatives operate in the city and are primarily devoted to organic food distribution. They have a very collaborative relationship, to the point that each covers a different city area: Mensakas works in Eixample and Sants, Les Mercedes works in Ciutat Vella, and Trèvol works in Nou Barris. These are supported by Biciclot, a cooperative bike workshop that assembles and maintains the cargo bikes and tricycles used for last-mile

distribution. Also, they have formed – together with similar coops from other Catalan cities – a second-degree coop called Som Ecològica. Som Ecològica focuses on designing, creating, and developing sustainable logistics systems at different levels. They have recently been working on a proposal to improve the distribution of agroecological food from Catalan territory in Barcelona. It is important to note that the distribution of agroecological food has recently become a political priority in the SSE plans of the public administration.

4.4.1.3 Commercialisation

The commercialisation sector is the more consolidated and numerous within the food SSE in Barcelona. The boundaries with the distribution sector are sometimes blurry, and many commercial initiatives also include food distribution exclusively for their purposes. This report classifies commercialisation FSIs into four categories: consumer groups and coops, bigger-scale consumer coop projects, bio shops, and direct sales. Consumer coops and groups are collective purchase projects in which a group of people self-organise their sourcing of proximity and organic food by dealing directly with producers. They are generally politicised projects based on self-organisation and direct democracy that mobilise discourses around food sovereignty and agroecology. Since the establishment of Germinal in 1993, consumer coops and groups experienced relatively rapid growth in Barcelona. After reaching a peak at the beginning of the 2010s, the number of initiatives in the city has stabilised at about 60, with around 3,500 members (Miró & Fernández, 2016). The formats and organisational models of consumer groups have evolved and diversified. The different models maintain common principles and criteria regarding the products that are consumed. Two organisational trends are observed: models that encourage a high degree of socio-political involvement to promote a profound change in the relational, consumption and production model and models looking for greater ease in the access of ecological products to broader and less active layers of society (Miró & Fernández, 2016). The most militant consumer groups rarely surpass 50 family units, often requiring active involvement and occasional labour from them. These characteristics and the recent stabilisation of their growth have led many people to believe that consumer groups and coops will never be able to transcend a niche of militant people. This diagnosis has fuelled the development of what we refer to as bigger-scale consumer coop projects. Whereas bigger-scale consumer coop projects maintain core groups of militantly engaged people, purchase does not necessarily require active involvement. Therefore, people in different moments of life and circumstances that make participation in these initiatives difficult can still access more affordable organic and local food. It can also be regarded as a strategy led by the cooperative participants to democratise access to organic, local, and healthy food. In Barcelona, there are two main examples of this type of food-related SSE. The Economat Social, is a well-established project with two stores in Sants and Nou Barris; and ^[OBJ] FoodCoop, a cooperative supermarket established in 2022 with a shop in l'Eixample. Another type of food-related SSE are bio shops. These are usually small grocery stores that sell organic products from organic producers. Interestingly, an independent stores' cooperative called Naturasí (formerly known as Molsa) has recently emerged. With 19 shops in Catalonia and Valencia (8 in Barcelona), Naturasí's model combines wholesale purchases for the whole network with some direct support to local farmers.

Last, there is also direct sales by producers, which is mainly exemplified in the “mercats de pagès” (farmers' markets). There are currently seven full-sized and three reduced farmers' markets in Barcelona. All of them take place weekly and are self-organised by neighbourhood organisations,

with the support of the Barcelona City Council. They only allow local organic farmers who are aligned with food sovereignty principles.

4.4.1.4 Catering

Another critical SSE sector is the catering sector. We can identify several types of initiatives: cooperative bars, restaurants, school canteens, catering projects and community kitchens. Many bars, restaurants, school canteens, and catering projects follow the SSE and support food sovereignty principles. These have formed several territorial networks (like in the Sants neighbourhood) and even a network of cooperative restaurants called XAREC. XAREC, which seems currently inactive, was established in 2013 and 22 organisations form it from Catalonia - some of them in Barcelona: *Cafè del centre, Ateneu democràtic i progressista, Espai cooperatiu de Cuina i Cultura Can Capablanca, El Velòdrom, Espai Culinari Cafè de Mar, Terra d'Escudella, La Barricon, L'Estraperlo, La Sargantana, Els Caus de Mura, La Fonda del Saumell, Can Ramon, Kop de mà, El Mirallet, La Clau, Koitton, Ateneu la Base, La Fàbrica. Cervesa Artesana Capfoguer, Cal Temerari, La Mà Negra. Espai gastronòmic del Casal Popular de Vilafranca, Centre Social Terra, Menjador Ca la Rosa y Taverna La Menuda*. As for community kitchens, these are fully-equipped kitchen facilities that serve a diversity of purposes, such as reducing food waste or promoting a healthy and sustainable food culture. Some are self-organised, like the Cuina de Can the City Council manages Batlló and others in collaboration with SSE organisations. Community kitchens are generally available to local organisations to organise food-related activities or cook for specific needs. Additionally, some are also available to support starting SSE catering projects. Two relevant examples are the Cuina Comunitària de Sant Antoni, and the Cuina de Ca L'Isidret.

4.4.1.5 Dynamisation

Last but not least, the dynamisation sector is not very numerous. Still, it is indeed very influential since they work primarily for public administration and significantly contribute to developing and executing SSE projects and strategies. We can identify two types of actors: those that deal with consultancy and research and those more concerned with communication and dissemination. The former group refers to those cooperatives that develop and coordinate specific initiatives and research about food sovereignty and agroecology. We could see them as the “expert knowledge” on which the public administration counts for implementing the existing SSE strategies. Whereas some focus exclusively on food (e.g., Arran de Terra), others have a broader focus, such as the ecosocial transition (e.g., Espai Ambiental). The latter group refers to a group of cooperatives active in disseminating practices and values around food sovereignty and agroecology through the publication of magazines, websites, and training. As in the previous category, some focus exclusively on food (e.g., El Pa Sencer, who edits the magazine *Soberanía Alimentaria*), while others have wider lenses, such as responsible consumption (e.g., Opcions). It is worth mentioning that many of the actors within the dynamisation sector have leading roles in key spaces of SSE coordination in Barcelona, such as Coòpolis, Agròpolis or the Comunalitats Urbanes.

4.5 The relationship between different food-related SSE actors

Food-related SSE actors in Barcelona have a generally positive relationship with each other and the public administration, as shown by the emergence of many formal and informal collaboration spaces over the years. There have been several attempts at creating formal spaces of collaboration

and coordination centered around (or partially overlapping with) the food-related SSE in Barcelona. However, these have proven to be unsuccessful due to the extreme heterogeneity of the sector, which makes it challenging to think that there can be a coordination structure that is useful for all (Interview 5), or due to the amount of effort put into coordination which do not match the actual scale of the food-related SSE (Interview 4). More successful have been collaborations based on territorial relations, funding opportunities, and specific campaigns or projects. Whereas *intercooperation* (i.e., cooperation and partnership among SSE stakeholders) remains one of the main pillars of the Catalan SSE movement, in the food sector, collaboration is often not systematised and heavily depends on personal relationships.

Many networks, platforms, organisations and institutional spaces foster collaboration between the SSE initiatives:

The **Network of Social Economy** (XES in Catalan) was created in 2003 and has more than 300 Catalan organisations (almost half of them in the province of Barcelona). The origins of this network trace back to the alter-globalisation movement and the relations established between Catalan and Brazilian cooperatives during the World Social Forum in Porto Alegre (2001). The XES is characterised by three main aspects: first, its international dimension; second, worker cooperatives are its foundations, given the historical and current importance of the cooperative movement in Catalonia; third, it has a political anti-capitalist and anti-system positioning (Giovannini, 2019).

The **Catalan Association on Social Economy** (AESCAT in Catalan) is a non-profit, fourth-level organisation that brings together the leading representation platforms of the different families of the social economy of Catalonia: the Confederation of Cooperatives of Catalonia, the Table of Entities of the Third Social Sector of Catalonia, the Business Confederation of the Third Social Sector of Catalonia, the Federation of Mutual Funds of Catalonia and the Solidarity Economy Network of Catalonia. Each of these families also mobilises different actors within the SSE. AESCAT brings together 7,422 organisations, 139,202 employees, a social base of 2.5 million people (cooperative members, members of organisations, mutualists...), and has a turnover of 7,853 million euros.

Driven by the Catalonia Social Economy Association (AESCAT) and the Barcelona City Council within the framework of the 2030 Barcelona Social and Solidarity Economy Strategy, the **City Agreement for the Social and Solidarity Economy Strategy** was approved in 2021. It is the result of a participative process started in February 2019 to develop a city strategy to promote and strengthen the social and solidarity economy in Barcelona. The City Agreement provides continuity and enhances that process while favouring joint work and shared governance of the SSE Strategy and guiding the future actions of the Barcelona City Council.

Agròpolis is a space of collaboration between the public administration, civil society, academia, and some economic actors to transform the Barcelona food system from a food sovereignty and agroecology perspective. Some SSE stakeholders are part of Agròpolis.

Another space of collaboration that aims to bring together agroecology with the SSE is **Einateca**, a platform of agroecological producers organised around local food networks led by L'Arستا, Arran de Terra, XES and Pam a Pam. Einateca aims to create small economies of scale that make distribution easier for agroecological producers in specific areas while also giving visibility to and strengthening mutual aid among small agroecological farmers. The platform, funded by the

Barcelona City Council, comprises 18 agroecological local food networks in Catalonia. This is not the only example of sectorial coordination and collaboration within the food-related SSE in Barcelona and beyond. In fact, the push for *intercooperation* mentioned above (which is highly encouraged by the different subsidy schemes) is proving moderately successful. Another example is Naturasí (formerly known as Molsa), mentioned above as part of the commercialisation initiatives. Naturasí has created a service cooperative that acts as a second-degree coop, enabling collective sourcing of processed organic products and reinventing the concept of the neighbourhood bio shop. Also, in the commercialisation sector, the different farmers markets in the city have recently created a coordinator to promote this type of initiative and defend their interests.

Another example is the Spanish network of cooperative supermarkets. Since there are only two of these initiatives in Barcelona, they have organised in a broader territorial network where they share concerns, and questions, and organise meetings. However, they mostly occasionally organise around specific emerging problems (Interview 1).

However, transversal collaboration can occasionally emerge in the form of symbiotic relationships. An example is the agroecological distribution strategy mentioned above, which several SSE stakeholders are developing under the umbrella of Coòpolis. One of the Mensakas riders summarises the collaborative approach in the following way:

“I believe that as cyclogistic operators, we can also take interesting commercial action for producers because we are going many places every day that maybe don’t know La Rural or other projects we work for. If we could take commercial action, we could increase the demand for agroecological products along the routes that we take daily”. (Interview 3).

Moreover, in the context of general coordination between SSE initiatives, several spaces of coordination and collaboration within the SSE include food as one of their strategic priorities. The most relevant of these are the Ateneus Cooperatius and the Comunalitats Urbanes. **Coòpolis** is the Ateneu Cooperatiu of Barcelona. It is a space run collectively by 37 SSE stakeholders and publically funded by the Catalan government to promote the creation of new cooperatives and generate employment opportunities within the SSE. Coopolis provides free counselling for potential entrepreneurs within the SSE, and it hosts an incubator program that gives premises and essential services at below-market prices for starting cooperatives. It also provides training opportunities that are open to everyone and runs campaigns that are aligned with the SSE’s strategic interests. Moreover, Coòpolis also has four “circles” (i.e., partially autonomous spaces organised around specific strategic lines). One of the circles deals with proposals for an ecosocial transition, taking food sovereignty as one of the three main pillars for achieving this goal. From the ecosocial transition circle, several coops coordinate to promote specific actions that bring about food sovereignty in the city, such as the recent development of a series of workshops for developing an agroecological food distribution strategy for Barcelona. As an interviewee pointed out, they aim to take this work one step further by:

“creating a coordinator that gathers stakeholders and takes forward the strategy of agroecological distribution, an attempt to coordinate all the involved agents” (Interview 4).

The Urban commonalities seek to complement the Ateneus Cooperatius by focusing on community economies and mobilising a broader concept of the SSE. It is helpful to understand Urban commonalities, as an interviewee states:

“[...]as an antenna of Coòpolis [*The Ateneu cooperatiu of Barcelona*]. We are like a metal detector searching for community initiatives that can be articulated into a formal SSE project” (Interview 6).

Besides the formal SSE stakeholders, Urban commonalities include community groups, mutual aid networks, and other similar initiatives. There are five Comunalitats Urbanes in Barcelona (Ciutat Vella, Sant Andreu, Nou Barris, Sarrià and Poble Sec), all of which include food sovereignty as a strategic axis. These are collectively run by consortiums of cooperatives, foundations, and other organisations, and they develop projects and activities based on disseminating food sovereignty values and bringing them together to populations living in poverty and precarity.

4.6 Main enablers and barriers to food-related SSE initiatives

4.6.1 Enablers

4.6.1.1 Public funding and institutional support

In the last few years, the Catalan and Barcelona governments have tried to boost the social and solidarity economy. This trend has been felt locally, particularly in Barcelona during Barcelona en Comú government, from 2015 to 2023. In fact, there is a general awareness that this is a great opportunity, as one interviewee put it:

[...] the amount of public resources currently available for the SSE has never existed before. And you can only find this in very few places in the world... If you compare historically and with other places, we are very privileged. (Interview 5)

Despite some criticism of the insufficient public funding and the excessive focus of the public administration on financial support, the multiple lines of subsidies are one of the most critical enablers of SSE activities. Beyond the direct economic support, the many programs and governance spaces allocate many types of resources (i.e., not only funding but also enabling spaces, fostering relations, etc) for food-related SSE. As one interviewee puts it:

“Regarding resources, the City Council supports SSE incubators in Barcelona. The council has also proactively sought to buy shops and other commercial spaces that were then leased on favourable terms. This type of action paves the way to starting initiatives”. (Interview 1)

4.6.1.2 Political will

Institutional support is usually mediated through Barcelona Activa, which offers entrepreneurs free business management training. Last but not least, the food-related SSE sector acknowledges that specific political mandates facilitate all the previously mentioned factors. Thus, political will emerges as an essential enabler to promote and boost the food-related SSE initiatives.

4.6.1.3 A widespread intercooperative culture

Another major enabler of the food SSE relates to the deeply rooted **culture of intercooperation**. As previously mentioned, finding common concerns and motivations that can articulate the whole

food-related SSE sector in Barcelona city and area of influence has been challenging. However, this has not prevented relentless cooperation both within and across sub-sectors based on specific interests or windows of opportunity. As an interviewee mentioned:

“There is an existing ecosystem of initiatives with different networks. This is an enabler because, being such a diverse ecosystem, with so many actors at different levels, it allows you always to find someone who can help you in case of trouble”. (Interview 1)

The degree and type of cooperation differ across sub-sectors and types of FSIs. Consumer groups and coops, for instance, tend not to embark on collective action among themselves. However, they have a symbiotic relationship with small producers, often helping kick-start or consolidate small projects. If one sub-sector is currently taking intercooperation one step further, though, it is distribution. Cyclologistics cooperatives, for instance, have informally agreed to divide the city of Barcelona instead of competing with each other. On a more formal front, thanks to a recent Singulars subsidy, they have created Som Ecològística, a second-degree coop that promotes and designs sustainable logistics systems. They also actively collaborate with other sub-sectors, such as production:

“We believe there are many similarities between the cyclologistics cooperatives and the organic farmers, in that most are small and isolated projects. If we all intercooperate, we can offer better services and become an alternative in the food sector, creating a different distribution model”. (Interview 3)

An important aspect of intercooperation is that, through their articulation in second-degree cooperatives or other suitable models, FSIs are able to create economies of scale that allow them to share expenses and reduce logistic costs, among other benefits. These alliances, moreover, also encourage the development of organisations seeking to enlarge their scale of action in search of a successful business model.

4.6.2 Barriers

4.6.2.1 Lack of stable and long-term funding

While there are specific funds for SSE from the Catalan and Barcelonan governments, many FSIs still believe that the public administration should raise the stakes and inject more funding within the SSE, particularly in the food sector, to achieve an agroecological transformation. As one interviewee said:

In my opinion, the agroecological transition will be subsidised or won't happen. It clearly must be subsidised. We need direct subsidies. (Interview 2)

4.6.2.2 Lack of institutional coherence

Despite the recent institutional efforts, one of the most relevant obstacles, according to several FSIs, is a lack of institutional coherence. As for the former, the public initiatives to promote food SSE initiatives in the past years have been centred around a single political figure. However, many other departments did not directly promote SSE with the same will:

“We find political will in ONE person, who has promoted many things. But the rest of the public structure is not aligned. It goes against it”. (Interview 4)

4.6.2.3 Bureaucracy

The bureaucracy required to justify using the subsidies obtained can be overwhelming for some projects. In fact, bureaucracy is especially a barrier for small cooperatives and organisations, which usually don't have the administrative infrastructure to cope with the required paperwork. This has two main undesirable consequences. First, it generates inequalities in the accessibility to public funds, where stakeholders with more administrative expertise (usually those with more considerable turnover) receive most of the subsidies. Second, it generates dynamics where applying for and, especially, justifying subsidies becomes the main activity of SSE stakeholders. An interviewee puts it this way:

We all need to justify our subsidy, and you must carry out certain activities each year. And often, things are done hurriedly and without content within the SSE. People do it with the only goal of justifying their subsidy, but they also make many people invest their time in attending these events. Ultimately, many of these activities are always the same, and we can invest our time and money in practical things. (Interview 2)

This situation puts some SSE stakeholders in a difficult situation where they must invest part of their workers' time in keeping the subsidy application-justification wheel spinning. This reduces the available time to do productive tasks that would allow them to improve their economic performance. Thus, situations of dependency are created where some SSE stakeholders' internal organisation is adapted to grant applying and justifying, and therefore need a constant input of subsidies. This is exacerbated by particular requirements imposed by some of the previously mentioned subsidies, as in the case of the Singulars grants:

[...] Each *Singulars* project, depending on how much they are awarded, implies the creation of new jobs. For a smaller project, it's one job. For larger projects, it is two. But having two full-time workers in a non-profit consumer coop is an expense that either you have many members and thus a lot of sales, or you can't afford. The result is that many projects have been born and have grown completely 'on steroids'. Once the steroids are over, it gets complicated. (Interview 1)

4.6.2.4 Access to infrastructure

The situation gets even worse for projects requiring some infrastructure, like workshops or storage spaces. The problem of price, in those cases, is exacerbated by the high density of the city and the general shortage of this type of space. But beyond the direct effect on food SSE businesses, these urban dynamics have also generated pressing housing problems, which force local populations to constantly move away from gentrifying neighbourhoods and eventually out of the city. This forced mobility prevents rootedness in the neighbourhood and the forging of long-lasting relations. Since SSE actors are generally rooted in a place and are based on values beyond the mere market transaction, this whole pattern has an apparent adverse effect on them since it reduces their potential customers.

4.6.2.5 External coordination exceeding internal productive capacity

There is also a general perception that the amount and scope of strategic plans and collaborative spaces recently developed do not match the actual productive capacity of the sector or its ability to attract new projects:

“We coordinate a lot, but in the end, we don’t do much actual work... it’s a mess. Because all these coordinating spaces are very cool, but we are all trying to organise things that are not actually there”. (Interview 4)

4.6.2.6 Lack of articulation of the food-related SSE sector

While the SSE sector is strongly articulated, notably, the food-related sector lacks this level of articulation. This is one barrier put forward by one interviewee working in public administration, who stated the difficulties stemming from the high level of atomisation of the subsector. These were related to a lack of common strategy by the SSE initiatives and entailed practical difficulties with the public administration. As he stated:

“From my position in public administration, I would have loved to have a very articulated and organised sector on the other side, to which it’d be easy to speak. It’s never easy, to be honest, but the food SSE sector is very atomised, and you don’t have a single point of contact that unites all interests”. (Interview 5)

4.6.2.7 Operational slowness

The participative and democratic governance of many SSE initiatives delays decision-making and creates operational slowness, posing another competitive disadvantage in the demanding and dynamic food market. In the case of cooperative supermarkets, for instance:

“Our reaction process is much slower than any private company with pyramidal management, and this is a significant structural problem”. (Interview 1)

4.6.2.8 Lack of entrepreneurship and business culture

There seem to be very few people willing to start new food SSE projects, and the few new initiatives emerging are tiny. For instance, in a 2024 free course on SSE entrepreneurship offered by Coòpolis, only three people were enrolled (Interview 4). On the other hand, many food SSE actors seem to be reluctant to acknowledge that, after all, they are businesses and thus need to operate as such. As an interviewee stated:

“Many projects have weak approaches to business and minimal business culture. And we need to strengthen that, from the perspective of the SSE, of course, because in the end, they are businesses, and they need to work, and the accounting sheet needs to be balanced”. (Interview 5)

This lack of entrepreneurship and business culture is also reflected in the size of the initiatives. Very few initiatives have successfully scaled up, and this is still one of the pending issues for the subsector to consolidate itself. At the same time, this hinders the opportunities for food-related SSE initiatives to expand and manage other arenas. As an interviewee stated:

“If you start a bidding process to manage all public canteens in Barcelona, for instance, who will enter the bid? There aren’t many projects [with that capacity]. The SSE need big projects to upscale” (Interview 2)

4.6.2.9 Urban development

Another set of obstacles has to do with geographical factors, both at the urban and regional levels. The first of these is the extraordinarily aggressive dynamics of urban development, with several

areas of the city heavily gentrified and others rapidly gentrifying. Affordable access to shops in the city, then, is an arduous task in such a stressed real estate market:

“We don’t have spaces! The square meter in Barcelona is inaccessible to everyone, so imagine for a small project, a small store...”. (Interview 4)

4.6.2.10 Limited Participation

Since these initiatives rely very much on participation and involvement from the people, the previously mentioned housing precarity and forced mobility are taking a toll on them:

“You get young people living in our neighbourhood with precarious jobs and paying 900€ for an irregular rent. And from night to day, the rent has risen to 1,200-1,300€. What do you think they are going to do? So this is the social landscape currently in Barcelona, and the same for the SSE and cooperativism”. (Interview 2)

4.7 The cultural and socio-political context shaping food-related SEE initiatives

The 2008 economic crisis prompted a comprehensive reassessment across the local political spectrum. Before this, the social economy had been included in initiatives targeting "vulnerable sectors", and the public sector advised on how to create cooperatives and labour societies in cases of company closures. However, with the crisis at its peak, municipalities started to integrate the solidarity economy into their strategies for local development (Miro & Fernandez, 2016).

When the political party Barcelona En Comú won the local government in May 2015, the SSE sector gained recognition as a significant player in economic governance. This acknowledgement led to the creation of a well-funded policy tool known as the [Impetus Plan for Social and Solidarity Economy in Barcelona \(2016-2019\)](#). About fifteen SSE entities were officially recognised for their involvement in shaping the plan, leading to the establishment of a participatory platform comprised of articulated SSE organisations dedicated to implementing the plan. From October 2015 onwards, the municipality has also been increasingly focusing on promoting a yearly SSE event in Catalonia. Also, collaborating with professionals in the SSE field and academia, several events were organised to involve public administrators and decision-makers, such as the 2018 Sharing Cities Summit, the 2017 Smart Cities Congress, and the 2015 and 2016 International Encounters on Municipalism and the Solidarity Economy (Eizaguirre, 2020).

Also, the parliamentary composition born from the Catalan elections of September 27, 2015, combined with the heat of the Catalan independence mobilisations, emphasised the significance of cooperativism in stimulating the economy and fostering sustainable, community-based development. Specifically, Resolution 17/XI of the Parliament of Catalonia of March 10, 2016, urges the Government to apply "measures dedicated to promoting the creation of new cooperatives and labour societies, especially by young people and unemployed people, especially older ones of fifty years", a resolution justified by the "social emergency, economic reactivation and the need for an institutional response" (Parlament de Catalunya, 2016).

Another crucial element that helps explain the presence and expansion of the SSE in Catalonia and Barcelona is the role that cooperativism has played in the region for decades. Cooperativism in Catalonia started in the mid-XIX century and steadily increased until the Second Republic, encouraged by workers' empowering ideologies. During the Francoist dictatorship, however, cooperativism experienced stagnation for decades but increased again during the 1970s. The number of cooperatives has oscillated for years, and since 2000, the number has decreased. Currently, Catalonia is the Spanish region with the highest number of cooperatives, a total of 4212 (Miró & Fernandez, 2016). The strength of social movements in Barcelona, which often are interwoven with and purchase services and products from the SSE sector, also supports the presence and expansion of this economic sector.

4.8 Conclusions

The data gathered in this report shows some of the most relevant aspects shaping the governance of food-related SSE initiatives in Barcelona. We categorised the different categories of food-related SSE initiatives, described the main regulations affecting these initiatives, and described the main City Council plans and programs affecting these initiatives and the primary sources of public funds they receive. We also identified this activity's main barriers and enablers and analysed these elements considering their cultural and socio-political contexts.

The findings show the relative strength of the SSE sector in general and the food-related subsector in Catalonia and Barcelona. This strength is related to the historical context, the influence of cooperativism and social movements in the region, the multi-scalar legal framework supporting the development of SSE, and the financial support granted by the regional and local governments. However, despite SSE's general support, the food-related subsector emerges as a weaker subsector, lacking articulation and a common strategy. To scale up and demonstrate a viable alternative, the food-related SSE subsector needs to continue receiving stable funding, visibility and other public support to secure long-term infrastructure and improve entrepreneurship and business culture. The subsector also seems to need to invest in partnerships and collaboration to expand their impacts, knowledge and experiences.

Results also show that the aggressive dynamics of urban development are one of the main barriers to food-related SSE. Further regulation and support are needed to secure spaces to develop food-related SSE initiatives. Also, despite demonstrating political will for advancing the SSE in general, administrations need to improve their institutional coherence and mainstream, for instance, executing SSE clauses in all public procurement, a major tool to promote food-related SSE publicly.

Lastly, food-related SSE is a fertile and promising avenue to advance the transformation of Barcelona's food system.

4.9 Recommendations

4.9.1 To the Barcelona City Council

- Grant specific and long-term funding to food-related SSE.

- Lighten the bureaucratic burden in food-related SSE initiatives, especially those with minimal technical structures.
- Enhance institutional coherence to transversalize the approach to SSE and the execution of food-related SSE clauses in public procurement.
- Promote collaborations among food-related initiatives to manage infrastructure and human resources jointly.
- Visibilise the food-related SSE sector, projects and impacts.
- Support the development of central purchases or wholesale warehouses for SSE initiatives.
- Support for food-related SSE initiative functioning infrastructure.
- Influence higher regulatory bodies and the private sector to limit the price of rental spaces in the city.
- Generate updated data about the food-related SSE sector in Barcelona.
- Generate participative spaces where the food-related SSE initiatives can express their positionings.
- Support the creation of a counselling network to advise food-related SSE initiatives.

4.9.3 To SSE organisations

- Create or strengthen food-related SSE initiatives coordination platforms to align interests and strategy.
- Increase visibility of the SSE initiatives and their impact.
- Encourage the participation of socially marginalised populations.
- Promote the training of the members of the initiatives, especially economic training.
- To avoid burnout, find a balance between the volume of remunerated tasks and those carried out from the militant commitment.
- Assess the social and environmental impacts of the initiatives based on social responsibility indicators.
- Improve coordination between projects to exchange services and create new ones.
- Participate in institutional processes to shape them with food-related SSE interests and grant visibility to the subsector.

4.9.3 To the private sector

- Collaborate with food-related SSE.
- Purchase products and services from food-related SSE initiatives.
- Consider becoming a food-related SSE initiative, especially if the business has strong foundations in social and environmental principles.
- Participate in training to transfer knowledge to food-related SSE initiatives, especially on business viability.

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